

Review and Perspectives on the Copyrolysis of Microalgal Biomass and Plastic Wastes

Michal Safar, Wei-Hsin Chen,* Dagmar Juchelkova, Helena Raclavska, Barbora Svedova, and Jamin Jamir Escalante

Cite This: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.5c06034>

Read Online

ACCESS |

Metrics & More

Article Recommendations

ABSTRACT: The escalating consumption of fossil fuels and the increasing accumulation of plastic waste have intensified the search for sustainable energy and waste management solutions. Microalgal biofuels represent a promising alternative due to their potential for reduced greenhouse gas emissions and a lower carbon footprint. However, bio-oil derived from microalgae typically exhibits high oxygen content, low volatility, and limited energy density, which restricts its direct utilization as a transportation fuel. Co-pyrolysis of microalgal biomass with plastic waste has emerged as an effective strategy to address these limitations, exploiting the hydrogen-rich and oxygen-deficient nature of plastics to enhance hydrocarbon formation and improve bio-oil yield and quality. This synergistic approach not only outperforms single-feedstock pyrolysis in terms of product yield and quality but also provides a viable valorization pathway for plastic waste. Despite the growing body of research on microalgae-plastic copyrolysis, understanding of the underlying synergistic mechanisms and optimal operating conditions remains fragmented, and a comprehensive review specifically dedicated to this feedstock combination is still lacking. Previous reviews have either considered biomass-plastic copyrolysis in a broad context or focused exclusively on microalgal biofuel conversion. This review presents an up-to-date and in-depth synthesis of microalgae and plastic copyrolysis. It critically evaluates synergistic effects and reaction mechanisms, compares conventional and advanced copyrolysis techniques, including fast, microwave-assisted, and catalytic pyrolysis, and assesses their impacts on the yield and quality of bio-oil, biogas, and biochar. The review ultimately identifies key research gaps and future directions, providing timely insights for advancing sustainable biofuel production and efficient plastic waste management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Following the development of biofuels in the first and second generations, microalgae have become a subject of interest thanks to their unique properties,^{1,2} which make them a potential raw material for the third and fourth generations of biofuel technology. The third generation involves transforming algae biomass into biofuels through various processing methods. On the other hand, the fourth generation focuses on algae's genetic processes to enhance their ability to produce biofuels.^{3,4}

Microalgae can be used to produce various biofuels through different processes. These biofuels include bioethanol, biomethane, bio-oil, biohydrogen, and biodiesel.^{5–8} Bioethanol is produced via fermentation, while biomethane is obtained via anaerobic digestion. Bio-oil is obtained through thermochemical processes,² while biohydrogen is made through direct biophotolysis. Biodiesel can be produced through transesterification⁹ or direct hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) of wet biomass.¹⁰ These biofuels derived from microalgae have the potential to serve as an alternative to fossil fuels, with lower greenhouse gas emissions and a reduced carbon footprint.¹¹

However, algal bio-oil has drawbacks, including high oxygen content, reduced volatility, and lower heating value (12–24 MJ kg⁻¹),¹¹ making it less practical for commercial applications. Therefore, enhancing algal bio-oil quality is crucial for developing strategies to reduce the formation of nitrogen-containing compounds and improve the bio-oil's properties, thereby increasing its feasibility for commercial applications. Microalgae have a limitation as a source of bio-oil because they are deficient in hydrogen, which can result in lower yields of hydrocarbons during the pyrolysis process. However, coprocessing microalgae with plastics can help address this issue, as plastics have a high hydrogen content and low oxygen content. This coprocessing can provide additional hydrogen during pyrolysis, thereby increasing hydrocarbon yields and enhancing bio-oil quality. Therefore, coprocessing microalgae

Received: November 17, 2025

Revised: January 22, 2026

Accepted: January 23, 2026

with plastics represents a promising solution to overcome the limitations of microalgae-based bio-oil production and enhance the economic feasibility of the process.¹²

Common features of plastic waste, including polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyethylene (PE), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), and polycarbonate (PC), are high volatile matter content, high viscosity, and high energy density due to very low humidity and ash content.^{13,14} Thus, the copyrolysis of microalgal biomass and plastics can potentially enhance the quality of pyrolysis oil and gas.¹⁵ Additionally, the thermal degradation of waste PE plastics can transform them into low-quality waxes, resulting in plant disruptions ranging from pipe blockages to reduced machine lifespans. The copyrolysis of microalgae biomass and PE can help promote chain splitting, polymer breaking, and better thermal degradation.^{15,16}

Co-pyrolysis contributes to the circular economy by transforming waste materials into useful products while reducing the environmental impact associated with conventional waste disposal methods.^{13,17} The copyrolysis of biomass with other wastes allows the transfer in one reactor without additional units.¹⁷ Co-pyrolysis refers to the concurrent thermal decomposition of different feedstocks, often resulting in improved yields and modified product profiles owing to synergistic interactions between the materials.^{3,12,18} The selection of input raw materials and the quality of the produced bio-oil depend on the elemental composition of the raw material, with the effective hydrogen index (EHI) being used to compare the feedstock and final quality.²⁰ Typically, the EHI of biomass feedstock ranges from 0 to 0.3,¹⁷ which increases to 0.8 after catalytic fast pyrolysis. Nevertheless, its value remains below that of diesel (EHI = 2.0).²¹ According to several studies, pyrolysis oil with an EHI exceeding 1.0 is considered appropriate for further refinement and potential application in internal combustion engines.¹⁶

Energy and mass product yields, as well as energy efficiency, are crucial factors to consider when studying the pyrolysis of algae and plastics, both individually and in copyrolysis. These parameters can provide valuable insights into the process's effectiveness and help optimize it for maximum yield and efficiency. Other factors, including heating rate, pyrolysis temperature, residence time, and mixing ratio, can also be varied to study their effects on product yields and energy efficiency.²²

The copyrolysis of microalgae and plastic waste is currently being intensively investigated as a promising thermochemical conversion technology, as it enables the production of higher-quality bio-oil while simultaneously addressing the challenge of plastic waste management.^{16,23–29} Numerous studies have demonstrated synergistic effects during copyrolysis, whereby the addition of hydrogen-rich plastics enhances bio-oil yield and improves its composition. For instance, copyrolysis effectively suppresses the formation of oxygenated and nitrogen-containing compounds in the oil,^{30,31} while a substantial fraction of chlorine from halogenated plastics is retained in the solid residue rather than being transferred to the liquid products. However, this technology faces several challenges. Pyrolysis bio-oil derived from microalgae typically contains high levels of heteroatoms, including oxygen (O) and nitrogen (N). In the case of coprocessing halogenated plastics such as PVC, the bio-oil also contains Cl, which contributes to its low stability and corrosiveness and therefore necessitates subsequent upgrading or standardization.^{16,18,23,32} Further-

more, scale-up to the industrial level has not yet been sufficiently demonstrated, and comprehensive assessments of environmental impacts using life cycle assessment (LCA) remain limited.^{16,18,24,33}

Earlier review articles have addressed the copyrolysis of various types of biomass and plastics in a general context,^{16,18,23,24} or the thermochemical conversion of algal biomass^{25,26} (in some cases also including the copyrolysis of microalgae with other waste streams²⁷). However, a detailed review specifically focused on the copyrolysis of microalgae and plastic wastes has been lacking.

Recent publications, as illustrated in Table 1,^{27–30,33,34} demonstrate a growing interest in this topic, highlighting the timeliness and necessity of such a comprehensive synthesis. Therefore, this review innovates in three main aspects. First, it provides a dedicated overview of the copyrolysis of microalgal biomass with plastic waste. Second, it integrates operating conditions and reactor designs with details on bio-oil, biogas, and biochar yield and quality. Lastly, it offers a mechanistic outlook summarizing synergies and kinetics for microalgae-plastic pairs, identifies key challenges, and outlines potential future research directions. In this way, the present article clearly distinguishes itself from previous reviews and fills a critical gap in the literature, providing valuable insights for the further development of sustainable biofuel production and efficient waste management strategies.

2. PYROLYSIS PROCESS

Pyrolysis is widely recognized as a highly developed and reliable thermochemical conversion technique for converting biomass under controlled conditions, typically involving elevated temperatures in an oxygen-free environment to produce energy carriers such as bio-oil (liquid), biochar (solid), and biosyngas (gas).^{35,36} The conditions under which pyrolysis occurs notably impact the resulting products' physical, chemical, and quantitative characteristics.³⁷ These products have diverse applications, including energy generation and environmental remediation, and have the potential to serve as viable substitutes for fossil fuels.^{38,39}

Furthermore, the comparison and discussion of diverse catalytic copyrolysis reactors encompasses examining varying feedstock-to-catalyst ratios, reactor temperatures, and additional operational parameters. Additionally, a thorough analysis delves into several catalytic processes, such as those employing ZSM-5 catalysts, transition metal catalysts, multipurpose catalysts, and ex-situ catalysts. The objective is to optimize the production of desired products, as highlighted in previous studies.^{3,18,40}

2.1. Classification of Pyrolysis Processes

Different pyrolysis methods, as shown in Figure 1, including slow, fast, and flash pyrolysis, have been established as practical and feasible routes for transforming various biomass materials.⁴² Innovative or nonconventional pyrolysis techniques are developed by altering traditional processes to enhance the yield, quality, and attributes of pyrolysis-derived products. Currently, advanced methods encompass a range of strategies, including catalytic pyrolysis, which utilizes catalysts to enhance and optimize the thermal decomposition process. Several advanced techniques integrate external technologies to improve the efficiency of the pyrolysis process, for instance, microwave-assisted pyrolysis, which enhances heating uniformity and energy efficiency. Moreover, emerging methods

Table 1. Overview of Review Articles on the Co-Pyrolysis of Microalgae and Plastics

article title	journal	year	literature coverage period	main focus of the review	refs
recent advances in copyrolysis of algal biomass with waste plastics for the production of upgraded oil and prospective	Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis	2026	up to 2025	synergistic mechanisms and kinetics of algal-plastic copyrolysis; effects on thermal decomposition behavior (including reduced activation energy, enhanced oil yield, and changes in product composition)	28
co-pyrolysis of microalgae and other biomass wastes for the production of high-quality bio-oil: progress and prospective	Bioresource Technology	2022	up to 2021	synergistic effects of copyrolysis of microalgae with various cofeedstocks (including plastics, waste tires, bamboo residues, etc.) on improving overall bio-oil yield and quality, with a critical evaluation of enhancements in heating value and fuel properties; special emphasis on catalytic effects	27
fueling sustainability: co-pyrolysis of microalgae biomass and waste plastics for renewable energy and waste mitigation	Biomass and Bioenergy	2024	up to 2024	comprehensive overview of the current state of microalgae-plastic waste copyrolysis from the perspective of sustainable energy production and waste minimization, including a detailed discussion of the physicochemical properties of microalgae and plastics and the synergistic benefits of their combined pyrolysis	29
advances in catalytic pyrolysis of mixed plastic waste with algal biomass: a review on sustainable biofuel production and carbon capture	Cleaner Waste Systems	2025	up to 2025	review of catalytic copyrolysis of mixed plastics in the presence of algal biomass for biofuel production and carbon sequestration, with an in-depth analysis of catalyst-assisted synergistic interactions between microalgae and various polymers and their effects on reaction pathways, cracking behavior, product selectivity, and dechlorination	30
review for the synergistic effects in catalytic copyrolysis of biomass and plastic waste: pathways to sustainable energy	Next Sustainability	2025	up to 2025	review of synergistic effects in the catalytic copyrolysis of biomass (particularly microalgae) and plastic wastes in the context of sustainable energy resources, focusing on the upgrading and valorization of copyrolysis products, especially the transformation of bio-oil and biochar into value-added chemicals and materials	33
co-pyrolysis of algae with other carbon-based materials: a review on synergistic products and molecular reaction pathway	Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry	2023	up to 2022	detailed review of algal copyrolysis with low-quality carbonaceous materials, with particular emphasis on synergistic product formation and molecular-level reaction mechanisms, including a critical discussion of recent experimental studies and advanced analytical techniques (TG, in situ FTIR, MS, Py-GC/MS) used for pyrolysate characterization	34

such as catalytic copyrolysis, hydrolysis, and microwave-assisted catalytic pyrolysis are being actively investigated. The central aim of these advanced approaches is to enhance the selectivity toward target pyrolytic products while optimizing operational conditions, specifically by reducing reaction temperatures and minimizing residence time, to maximize the output of desired compounds.³⁵ Table 2 presents various studies focused on the pyrolysis processes of microalgae, pyrolysis product yields, and the combination of pyrolysis modes and reactors.

2.1.1. Conventional Thermal Pyrolysis. **2.1.1.1. Slow Pyrolysis.** Slow pyrolysis is generally associated with experimental conditions that favor the formation of solid carbonaceous residues, as lower heating rates and longer residence times promote biochar production at the expense of liquid yields. In the case of microalgae, these conditions enhance char formation due to the high protein and mineral content of the biomass, while limiting the generation of condensable bio-oil. Consequently, slow pyrolysis is not considered an optimal pathway when the primary objective is the maximization of liquid biofuels from microalgal feedstocks.^{35,43}

2.1.1.2. Fast Pyrolysis. Fast pyrolysis is a well-established approach for converting microalgal biomass into bio-oil, as it enables high liquid yields through rapid heating and short vapor residence times. The fast-heating rates effectively suppress secondary reactions, such as cracking and polymerization of volatile intermediates, which is critical for preserving bio-oil quality. Due to its ability to process feedstocks with high ash and mineral content, fast pyrolysis is particularly suitable for microalgae, where inorganic components are concentrated in the resulting biochar, while liquid products remain the dominant.^{3,35,44}

2.1.1.3. Flash Pyrolysis. Flash pyrolysis, characterized by extremely short residence times and very high heating rates, has been investigated as a variant of fast pyrolysis; however, due to its limited industrial relevance, complex reactor design, and marginal applicability to microalgal biomass, it is generally not considered a practical route for large-scale bio-oil production.^{35,46}

2.1.2. Advanced or Modified Pyrolysis Technologies.

2.1.2.1. Catalytic Pyrolysis. Catalytic copyrolysis has been shown to significantly improve the quality of bio-oil produced from microalgae-plastic mixtures by reducing the content of oxygen- and nitrogen-containing compounds and increasing the proportion of light hydrocarbons. In particular, acidic zeolite catalysts, such as HZSM-5, effectively promote cracking and aromatization reactions, leading to the enhanced formation of monoaromatic hydrocarbons while suppressing oxygenated and nitrogenous fractions in the bio-oil. Several studies report that the presence of HZSM-5 during the copyrolysis of microalgae with polyolefin plastics results in higher hydrocarbon yields, lower acidity, and improved stability of the liquid product, demonstrating the practical relevance of catalytic upgrading for this feedstock combination.^{47–49}

2.1.2.2. Microwave Pyrolysis. Microwave-assisted pyrolysis (MAP) has emerged as a promising alternative heating method for converting microalgal biomass, as it enables rapid and more uniform heating compared to conventional pyrolysis. This enhanced heating efficiency promotes higher yields of gaseous products, particularly H₂- and CO-rich syngas, while reducing the content of ash and solid particles in the bio-oil. However,

Figure 1. Classification of pyrolysis routes and heating approaches.

Table 2. A List of Microalgae Pyrolysis^a

feedstock	type of pyrolysis	reactor type	catalyst	particle size	temperature (°C)	yield wt %			refs
						bio-oil	gas	char	
Dunaliella salina	slow	fixed-bed	-	45–150 μm	500	55.4	3.9	28	106
Dunaliella tertiolecta	slow	fixed-bed	-	-	500	24	13	63	72
Spirulina platensis	slow	batch	-	-	350	23.8	19.2	39.7	107
Spirulina sp	slow	fixed-bed	-	0.5–1 mm	550	21	23	21	108
Spirulina platensis	slow	batch	-	-	500	28.5	28	25.6	107
Chlorella vulgaris	slow	fixed-bed	-	-	500	41	22	37	72
Chlorella sp	microwave	fixed-bed	-	-	480	28.6	26.5	24.5	109
Chlorella sp	microwave	fixed-bed	HZSM-5	-	550	28.6	16	25	49
Nannochloropsis sp	microwave	fixed-bed	HZSM-5	-	500	36.2	18	25	49
Chlorella vulgaris	fast	fluidized	-	420–700 μm	500	53	10	31	110
Chlorella protothecoides	fast	fluidized	-	<0.18 mm	500	17	29	54	111
Chlorella	catalytic	fixed-bed	Na ₂ CO ₃	-	300–450	35–55	-	-	53
Nannochloropsis sp. residue	catalytic	fixed-bed	HZSM-5	-	300–500	30.8–45.8	12.9–35.7	20.1–57	112
Chlorella	catalytic	fixed-bed	Fe-ZSM-5	<90 μm	500	43.1	27.1	29.7	113
Chlorella pyrenoidosa	hydropyrolysis	batch	-	-	150–450	12.2–53.2	2.2–21.2	12.3–74	114
Chlorella pyrenoidosa	catalytic hydropyrolysis	batch	Pt/C	100 mesh	400–450	33.09	7.67	6.95	51
Spirulina platensis	catalytic hydropyrolysis	batch	Pt/C	100 mesh	400–450	33.45	5.50	16.45	51

^aNot reported.

due to the inherently low microwave absorption capacity of microalgae, the addition of suitable microwave absorbers, such as activated carbon, SiC, or char, is typically required to achieve effective heating and stable process operation. Despite these advantages, research on the application of MAP to microalgae remains limited, and further studies are needed to evaluate its scalability and techno-economic feasibility.^{2,25,39,50}

2.1.2.3. Hydropyrolysis. In a specific variation of pyrolysis known as hydropyrolysis (HyPy), biomass decomposes in high-pressure hydrogen (0.1–8 MPa). This emerging technique entails the conversion of algal biomass using pressurized hydrogen-based technologies, primarily aimed at producing high-quality pyrolytic oil with high proportions of saturated hydrocarbons (from 57.98 to 95.82%),⁵¹ such as lowering the oxygen content in the resulting bio-oil, suppressing char generation, and incorporating trace amounts of hydrogen into the pyrolytic liquid products. Furthermore,

hydrocarbons produced through hydropyrolysis exhibit enhanced structural preservation and stability.^{25,35}

2.2. Pyrolysis Reactors

The reactor type is crucial in effectively transforming organic materials into energy in the form of gaseous, liquid, or solid fuels through the pyrolysis process. Various reactor configurations have been reported for microalgae pyrolysis; however, as summarized in Table 1, fixed-bed reactors are by far the most commonly employed setup in experimental studies. This preference reflects their simplicity, robustness, and suitability for laboratory-scale investigations of microalgal feedstocks, including catalytic and microwave-assisted pyrolysis.²

2.3. Pyrolytic Products

Pyrolysis produces three main fractions: bio-oil, biochar, and pyrolytic gas, whose ratio depends on the process conditions.⁴⁶

2.3.1. Bio-Oil. Bio-oil derived from microalgae exhibits greater stability than bio-oil obtained from conventional crops,

such as wood, although it falls short of the stability levels seen in fossil fuels. The composition of the resulting bio-oil primarily consists of aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons, phenols, long-chain fatty acids, and nitrogen-containing compounds. Oil yields as high as 40% can still be achieved even at a low temperature of 300 °C. The calorific value (CV) of bio-oil derived from microalgae biomass is between 30.7 and 41 MJ kg⁻¹, while its viscosity is around 0.061 Pa.⁵² Bio-oil offers advantages over fossil fuels, including renewability and lower emissions of NO_x and SO_x. Nonetheless, bio-oil possesses undesirable characteristics, such as high moisture content, elevated viscosity, low ignition quality, and corrosive behavior, necessitating its upgrading before use as a fuel.⁴⁶ Employing catalytic pyrolysis can lead to higher oil yields with reduced oxygenated compounds without affecting the overall yield. The percentage of oxygenated compounds in catalytic bio-oil is 19.5%, whereas 30% is generated via direct pyrolysis. The catalyst employed in the process can be reused in the pyrolysis reactor, further improving its efficiency. Using Na₂CO₃ as a catalyst, an energy recovery rate of approximately 40% can be achieved in the catalytic pyrolysis of bio-oil with reduced acidity.^{52,53}

2.3.2. Biochar. Throughout the pyrolysis process, approximately 10–25% of the biomass undergoes conversion into char, which refers to solid carbon particles with a porous structure.^{45,83} The biochar that is produced is a result of the reactive pyrolysis vapor. It has been noted that the residual biochar accounts for approximately one-third of the original microalgae biomass.⁵² In summary, temperature, residence time, and biomass composition are key factors to affect biochar yield. The optimal temperature range for biochar production typically falls between 450 and 600 °C, depending on the type and characteristics of the biomass. For enhanced char production, slow pyrolysis is preferred under conditions such as low heating rates, minimal carrier gas flow, elevated pressure, and the use of relatively large biomass particles (typically in the millimeter scale) that possess low moisture content and high lignin concentrations. The impact of catalysts on biochar yield is complex; however, acid catalysts, such as ZnCl₂, ZSM-5, and ZnO, enhance biochar production and improve product quality.⁴⁶

2.3.3. Biogas. Pyrolysis of microalgal biomass typically yields a relatively low fraction of gaseous products (often below 20 wt %), although the resulting gas has a high calorific value and is commonly used to partially meet the process's energy demand. During copyrolysis with plastics, particularly hydrogen-rich polymers producing light hydrocarbons, the gas yield can increase, accompanied by a higher content of combustible components. This synergy enhances the overall energy efficiency of the process and improves the energetic value of the gaseous fraction.³⁵ The energy content of the gaseous products typically falls within the range of 10 to 35 MJ kg⁻¹. Factors such as processing temperature, vapor residence time, and the inclusion of additives significantly influence both the yield and the chemical composition of the resulting biogas.²⁵

2.4. Summary

Pyrolysis serves as a versatile thermochemical platform for microalgal biomass conversion, yielding bio-oil, biochar, and syngas, with their distributions determined by process parameters such as heating rate, temperature (300–600 °C), and residence time. Fast pyrolysis maximizes liquids, up to 40

wt % at around 300 °C, with an HHV of 30.7–41 MJ kg⁻¹, while suppressing secondary cracking. While slow pyrolysis favors biochar production (10–25 wt %, optimal temperature between 450 and 600 °C), advanced variants enhance selectivity and quality. Catalytic pyrolysis (e.g., HZSM-5) promotes cracking/aromatization to boost hydrocarbons and reduce O/N content, while microwave-assisted pyrolysis delivers uniform heating for H₂/CO-rich syngas, and hydro-pyrolysis (0.1–8 MPa H₂) yields 58–96% saturated hydrocarbons by lowering bio-oil oxygen content and suppressing char generation.

3. CO-PYROLYSIS EXPERIMENT CONDITIONS

Co-pyrolysis experiments reported in the literature indicate that the outcome of microalgae-plastic coprocessing is governed by a limited set of key experimental parameters, among which feedstock composition, mixing ratio, operating temperature, heating rate, residence time, and reactor configuration play dominant roles.^{23,27} These factors determine whether synergy is advantageous or detrimental. Among them, the composition of blended feedstock significantly influences synergistic effects, rendering copyrolysis complex and diverse.²³ Across studies, a consistent trend emerges: the addition of hydrogen-rich plastics generally facilitates the thermal decomposition of microalgal biomass, promotes volatilization, and shifts product distribution toward higher liquid and gaseous yields, while suppressing char formation. At the same time, variations in experimental setup, such as batch versus continuous reactors, inert versus reactive atmospheres, or the presence of catalysts, can significantly modify reaction pathways and product selectivity. The following subsections therefore discuss these experimental conditions in detail, focusing on how individual parameters and their combinations influence copyrolysis behavior and enable meaningful comparison across reported studies.

3.1. Feedstock

Characterizing feedstocks is a critical step in thermal conversion processes, as their unique chemical compositions and physical attributes significantly influence reaction behavior and product distribution. The characterization process involves proximate and ultimate analysis measurements.⁵⁴ The organic composition and content of biomass feedstocks predominantly indicate their quality. In addition to proximate and ultimate analysis, the primary components of organic matter in biomass feedstocks include carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids. The proportions of these components may vary depending on the type of biomass. Algae biomass contains high levels of protein, lipids, and some carbohydrates. Conversely, plastics are primarily polymers with a high hydrocarbon content.⁵⁵ Ultimate analysis determines the elements present in the samples, including the percentage of C, H, O, N, and S, as well as their associated ratios, such as H/C and O/C.⁵⁴ The calorific value of the oil can be significantly affected by its carbon and hydrogen content. However, biomass pyrolysis produces high-oxygen-content and acidic bio-oil, leading to unstable and corrosive liquid products.⁵⁶

Biomass pretreatment plays a crucial role in conversion processes by enhancing the accessibility and reactivity of its constituents for various downstream applications. Several pretreatment methods exist, including physical, chemical, physical-chemical, biological, thermal, and combined pretreatments. Common pretreatment methods, such as drying,

Table 3. A List of Various Microalgal Species and Their Ultimate and Proximate Analysis Used in Co-Pyrolysis Process with Plastics^a

microalgae biomass	ultimate analysis [dry basis, wt %]					calorific value [MJ kg ⁻¹]	proximate analysis [dry basis, wt %]							refs
	C	H	O	N	S		volatile	ash	moisture	fixed carbon	lipids [wt %]	proteins [wt %]	carbohydrates [wt %]	
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	47.32	5.97	27.85	11.33	0.70	19.63	82.30	6.83	-	10.87	-	-	-	71
<i>Nannochloropsis</i> sp	50.61	7.31	24.75	6.68	0.64	21.51	79.61	6.00	4.01	10.38	30.00	40.8	19.20	15
<i>Nannochloropsis</i> sp	50.67	7.35	35.44	6.54	-	21.36	80.74	7.16	4.30	7.80	36.5	32.7	30.8	48
<i>Dunaliella salina</i>	45.75	6.91	43.08	4.11	0.15	-	81.8	0.22	-	17.98	10.50	58.82	11.87	19
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	48.30	7.15	35.04	9.01	0.50	21.58	65.85	8.82	7.71	17.62	-	-	-	78
<i>Spirulina platensis</i>	47.58	6.33	28.15	11.26	0.51	18.68	81.13	6.17	7.62	5.08	10.30	65.20	10.71	31
<i>Nannochloropsis</i> sp	50.61	7.31	28.46	6.68	0.64	21.51	79.21	6.30	4.23	10.26	30.00	40.80	18.67	31
<i>Dunaliella tertiolecta</i>	43.31	5.96	29.90	4.33	-	17.81	64.70	16.50	1.60	17.20	5.18	30.63	52.31	69
<i>Chlorella</i> sp	49.11	7.14	28.97	8.59	0.77	-	79.17	5.42	-	15.41	10.30	58.50	25.78	12
<i>Chlorella sorokiniana</i> residue	53.84	7.18	32.16	6.57	0.25	22.86	78.85	3.14	-	17.71	-	-	-	60
<i>Nannochloropsis</i> sp	48.43	7.33	35.04	8.04	1.16	20.81	78.08	7.16	4.31	10.45	8.21	54.37	25.95	58
<i>Spirulina</i>	44.6	6.91	37.4	10.5	0.65	23.1	75.3	5.8	5.5	13.0	-	-	-	38
fresh water algae, Sabarmati river, India	46.5	5.5	42.8	5.1	0.1	18.4	80.7	8.8	-	10.5	-	-	-	85
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	48.30	7.15	35.04	9.01	0.5	21.58	65.85	8.82	-	17.62	-	-	-	92
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	47.62	7.00	24.84	11.56	0.7	21.55	78.43	8.28	2.36	10.92	-	-	-	86,88

^aNot reported.

torrefaction, milling, and sieving, are widely applied to improve sample uniformity and ensure homogeneity prior to thermal conversion. Proper drying is essential for reducing the moisture content in biomass, as high moisture levels can negatively impact the yield and quality of the produced bio-oil. The elevated moisture content in pyrolysis oil contributes to its lower energy density, diminishing its attractiveness as a fuel source. The primary origins of water in pyrolysis oil are the moisture present in the feedstock and the dehydration processes that occur during the pyrolysis process. However, using dry feedstock is not practical due to the high costs associated with drying.

Co-pyrolysis has emerged as an efficient approach for managing the water content within pyrolysis oil. Plastics have much lower water content, resulting in lower water content in the resulting oil. Therefore, adding plastics as feedstock in pyrolysis can help lower the oil's water content.²³ In general, pretreatment represents one of the most cost-intensive stages in biomass conversion, primarily due to its high energy demands. The choice of pretreatment technique should be carefully aligned with the specific properties of the biomass, available capital investment, process operating conditions, and associated environmental impacts. Selecting a suitable pretreatment method can enhance the effectiveness of the subsequent copyrolysis process, leading to a more desirable set of end products.²⁷ For industrial applications, incorporating internal heat sources via process integration can be employed to fulfill the heat requirements for drying feedstock. Researchers propose that byproducts, such as char or gas, for combustion can supply the required heat for endothermic pyrolysis and other intermediate processes like drying of biomass.²³

3.1.1. Microalgal Biomass. The pyrolysis of microalgae is a fascinating and unique research field due to its significant differences in composition compared to cellulosic biomass. Based on ultimate analysis data, the carbon content in these algal species typically accounts for 40% to 50% of their total

dry weight (TDW), while the H content is approximately 7% of TDW. The N content, ranging from 3.1% to 10.6%, directly correlates with the protein content of microalgae, whereas the S content in microalgae is relatively low, ranging from 0.5% to 1.5%. The volatile matter constitutes 69% to 81% of TDW, while the fixed carbon content accounts for 10% to 16% of TDW in microalgae.⁴⁰ Microalgae, which utilize sunlight, water, and carbon dioxide to grow, exist as single-celled organisms and can range in size from nanometers to millimeters. Microalgae generally consist of diverse biochemical constituents, including lipids (7–23%), carbohydrates (4–57%), and proteins (6–71%). Among these, lipids are particularly important for biofuel applications. Under optimal growth conditions, specific microalgal strains are capable of accumulating lipids that constitute 50–70% of their total dry biomass.⁵⁷ Numerous research studies have shown the optimal cultivation methods for microalgae with high lipid content. Several common species, including *Nannochloropsis*, *Chlorella*, and *Spirulina*, are promising feedstocks for biodiesel production. Information on the composition, ultimate analysis, and proximate analysis of various representative microalgal strains are provided in Table 3.

Environmental factors, such as pH, salinity, nitrogen (N) levels, and light intensity, are commonly used to induce the production of lipids, carbohydrates, and other valuable compounds. Nitrogen and phosphorus are essential nutrients for the growth of microalgae and their production of lipids. It has been observed that depriving microalgae of nutrients increases their lipid content but hampers cell growth. Microalgae cultivation can be divided into two phases to overcome this growth limitation. An adequate nitrogen supply is provided in the first phase to promote biomass production. In the second phase, N deprivation is implemented to induce lipid accumulation. In nutrient-depleted conditions, the demand for membrane lipids diminishes, leading to a higher conversion of fatty acids into neutral lipids. Cell growth is then

impaired, which leads to all the available carbon being converted into lipids instead of proteins.⁹

Based on their composition, microalgae can be broadly divided into high-lipid algae, typically containing 20–30% lipid content, and high-protein algae, which often have protein levels ranging from 30% to 63%.¹² The conversion process commonly used for microalgae usually demands strains with high lipid content. Nevertheless, such strains typically exhibit lower biomass productivity.⁵⁸ In terms of yield and quality, oils extracted from lipid-rich microalgae demonstrate clear advantages compared to those sourced from algae with lower lipid content. Nevertheless, cultivating high-lipid microalgae typically requires stressful conditions, which can result in reduced productivity.²¹ Conversely, high-protein microalgae typically thrive in natural habitats or under conditions with ample nitrogen, resulting in significantly higher productivity. Regrettably, the protein content in such microalgae can undergo depolymerization into various nitrogen-containing compounds, consequently elevating the nitrogen content (ranging from 3% to 8%) in bio-oil.^{9,12} When microalgae are pretreated and their protein content is reduced, the resulting pyrolytic bio-oil contains fewer N-containing compounds and is mainly composed of long-chain fatty acids. Using catalysts, it is feasible to transform these fatty acids into hydrocarbons efficiently.⁵⁹

The study of Lv et al.¹² prepared *Chlorella* sp. by hydrothermal pretreatment at a temperature of 175 °C. This process was intended to remove some of the N content from the sample.⁵⁹ Additionally, the oil had high levels of carbon (68.50%) and hydrogen (9.70%) and was notable for having a relatively lower nitrogen content (5.31–8.01%) compared to other algal bio-oils.¹² In the research of Kumar et al.,⁶⁰ the microalgae *Chlorella sorokiniana* (CSR) was hydrothermal treatment within a temperature range of 150–250 °C. This led to an increased nitrogen content being absorbed into the liquid phase. At the same time, the residue from hydrothermally treated *Chlorella sorokiniana* was used to examine the copyrolysis process of waste polymers (specifically PS and waste tires). The residue showed a higher carbon content, fixed carbon, and lower ash content compared with untreated microalgae.⁶⁰

3.1.2. Plastics. Plastics have emerged as fundamental materials in our daily existence, serving various purposes and finding applications in various domains. They are extensively utilized across various sectors, including packaging, medical equipment, electronic devices, and numerous other applications. However, the accelerated production of disposable single-use plastics has given rise to a worldwide pollution predicament. To address this issue, employing plastic waste as an energy source presents a promising solution.⁶¹ The primary plastics commonly found in municipal solid waste (MSW) include PE, LDPE, HDPE, PP, PS, PVC, and PET. Packaging materials constitute the most significant proportion, accounting for 50–70% of overall plastic disposal, primarily composed of polyolefins (PE, PP, PS, and PVC).⁶² Unlike biomass, plastic materials contain a high amount of hydrogen, minimal oxygen, and a high proportion of volatiles.⁶³ Table 4 shows the ultimate and proximate analyses of different plastics.

Incorporating more volatile substances in copyrolysis leads to increased gas or oil production. One key mechanism in the copyrolysis of biomass and plastics involves the transfer of hydrogen atoms from the plastic component to the biomass. The released volatiles from plastics can undergo secondary

Table 4. Ultimate and Proximate Analysis of Plastics^a

material	ultimate analysis (dry basis, wt %)				calorific value [MJ kg ⁻¹]	proximate analysis (dry basis, wt %)				refs	
	C	H	O	N		S	volatile	ash	fixed carbon		moisture
PE	85.81–91.90	8.10–13.86	0.00	0.00–0.12	0.00–0.06	44.7	97.40–99.85	0.15–2.20	0.00–0.40	0.00–0.02	85,115
PP	81.20–92.4	7.6–14.38	0.00–4.59	0.00–0.24	0.00–1.92	42.45–46.17	94.60–100.00	0.00–1.20	0.00–4.20	0.00–0.21	12,19,48,69,78,88
PS	89.98–92.07	7.89–8.52	0–0.95	0.00–0.45	0.03–0.30	40.39–42.73	94.95–99.57	0.04–2.13	0.39–2.86	0.00–0.08	19,58,60,85
PET	61.80–62.00	4.55–5.36	33.55	0.02–0.03	0.01–0.08	24.04	84.80–85.40	0.40–0.90	13.70–14.80	0.00–0.40	19,116
PVC	38.09–41.72	4.35–5.22	0.00–0.63	0.00–0.41	0.00–0.45	20.07–20.50	90.18–94.60	0.00–0.17	4.50–9.82	0.00–0.90	19,38,71
HDPE	84.29–85.09	13.40–14.20	0.86	0.00	0.00–0.01	44.24	96.50–99.99	0.01–1.80	0.00–1.70	0.00–0.20	86,87,116,117
LDPE	84.32	15.47	-	0.00–0.20	0.02–0.21	43.39–47.29	93.80–99.99	0.01–5.00	0.00–1.20	0.00–0.20	15,31,116

^aPolyethylene (PE); polyvinyl chloride (PVC); polypropylene (PP); polystyrene (PS); polyethylene terephthalate (PET); high-density polyethylene (HDPE); low-density polyethylene (LDPE).

Table 5. Summary of Recent Progress and Previous Studies on Co-Pyrolysis of Microalgae and Plastics Using Different Mixing Ratio

feedstock microalgae-plastics	blends ratio	pyrolysis conditions	results	refs
Chlorella vulgaris PVC	1:9, 2:7, 5:5, 7:3, 9:1	microwave 800 and 1000 W, N ₂ 300 mL·min ⁻¹	increasing the proportion of PVC significantly reduces nitrogen- and oxygen-containing compounds in the liquid phase (from 29.65% to 0.38% at 800 W), while simultaneously decreasing solid residue yield and increasing the heating value of the products; PVC also promotes the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons	71
Nannochloropsis sp./LDP	100:0, 25:75, 33:67, 50:50, 67:32, 75:25, 0:100	fixed bed reactor: 600 °C, Ar 150 mL·min ⁻¹	co-pyrolysis increased the gas yield and facilitated the production of CH ₄ and C ₃₊ . The liquid product exhibited a decrease in oxygen- and nitrogen-containing compounds	15
Nannochloropsis sp./PP	1:0, 3:1, 2:1, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 0:1	TGA and fixed bed reactor: 500–900 °C, 20 °C·min ⁻¹ , Ar, 200 mL·min ⁻¹ , catalyst: HZSM-5	polypropylene (PP) accelerated the thermal degradation of Nannochloropsis sp. (NS) and reduced its pyrolysis temperature. In contrast, the presence of NS caused a slight increase in the peak pyrolysis temperature of PP	48
Dunaliella salina PP, PS, PET, PVC	1:1	TGA: 800 °C, 20 °C·min ⁻¹ , N ₂ , 100 mL·min ⁻¹	molten plastics exert a catalytic-like effect on microalgal decomposition, leading to reduced activation energies; copyrolysis particularly accelerates the thermal degradation of PET and PVC	19
Chlorella vulgaris PP	1:1	TGA: 900 °C, N ₂ 50 mL·min ⁻¹ , 20 °C·min ⁻¹ , catalysts: ZSM-5, CaO	the presence of PP was vital in accelerating the pyrolysis of CV and lowering the temperature of initial pyrolysis. PP enhanced the C–H and C=C peaks and decreased the signals related to N- and O-containing compounds	78
Chlorella vulgaris HDPE	4:1	TGA: 900 °C, N ₂ 100 mL·min ⁻¹ , 10, 20, 30, 50, 100 °C·min ⁻¹ , catalysts: LS, HZSM-5	the peak degradation rate of the binary blends was lower than the highest rate observed for pure HDPE. Pyrolysis of the CV/HDPE mixture resulted in lower residues (6.43–12.02%) compared to the pyrolysis of CV (13.79–32.58%), primarily due to the inclusion of HDPE	87
Nannochloropsis sp., Spirulina pla- tensis/LDPE	3:1	fixed bed reactor: 600 °C, Ar, 150 mL·min ⁻¹	co-pyrolysis successfully suppressed the formation of N and O compounds while increasing the production of long-chain alcohols and formic/acetic acid esters. A noticeable reduction in N and O content was observed in the copolytic oil	31
Dunaliella tertiolec- ta/PP	100:0, 80:20, 60:40, 40:60, 20:80, 0:100	TGA: 800 °C, N ₂ 50 mL·min ⁻¹ , 5, 10, 20, 40 °C·min ⁻¹	the strongest interaction between polypropylene (PP) and Dunaliella tertiolecta was observed at a mixing ratio of 6:4. In this blend, PP lowered the apparent activation energy of the microalgae from 166.9 kJ·mol ⁻¹ to 144.2 kJ·mol ⁻¹ . This effect may be attributed to interactions between PP and functional groups such as CO ₂ or carbonyls, which likely contributed to the observed decrease in CO ₂ generation	69
Chlorella sp./PP	100:0, 80:20, 60:40, 40:60, 20:80, 0:100	TGA: 900 °C, Ar, 20 °C·min ⁻¹	the introduction of PP speeded up the pyrolysis process of ChSR and inhibited the release of C ₂ H ₅ O ⁺ /COOH ⁺ and NH ₃ while it supported the release of CO ₂ . The interaction of ChSR and PP significantly promoted the formation of hydrocarbons	12
Chlorella sorokimi- ana/PS	1:1	TGA: 800 °C, N ₂ 50 mL·min ⁻¹ , 10, 20, 30 °C·min ⁻¹ ; fixed-bed reac- tor: 500 °C, Ar, 10 °C·min ⁻¹	fuels interaction promoted hydrocarbons and impeded O- and N-containing compounds. Co-pyrolysis accelerated the degradation rate and shifted the reaction temperature to the lower range	60
Nannochloropsis sp. PS	100:0, 25:75, 35:65, 50:50, 65:35, 75:25, 0:100	TGA: 800 °C, N ₂ 50 mL·min ⁻¹ , 10, 20, 30 °C·min ⁻¹	the 75% and 65% NS content mixtures showed the most pronounced synergistic effect. The results indicate that including PS increased the oil yield by 42.70% compared to the pyrolysis of NS alone	58
Spirulina PVC	25:75, 50:50, 75:25	TGA: 600 °C, Ar 40 mL·min ⁻¹ , 5, 10, 15, 20 °C·min ⁻¹	MA-PVC had a significantly lower apparent activation energy in blends than MA and PVC. PVC postponed the degradation of microalgae	38
Chlorella vulgaris HDPE	1:1	microwave 800 W, N ₂ 700 mL·min ⁻¹ , catalysts: activated carbon—AC, Ni, Fe, Ce	significant enhancement of copyrolysis performance is achieved in the presence of catalysts; the highest bio-oil yield (25.6%) was obtained using 40 wt % Fe supported on activated carbon (Fe/AC)	86
Chlorella vulgaris HDPE	4:1, 2:1, 1:1, 1:2, 1:4	microwave 800 and 1000 W, N ₂ 700 mL·min ⁻¹ , catalyst: activated carbon AC 10–50%	the ideal blending proportion of CV and HDPE was 1:1, HDPE reduced the N compounds by 75.75%. Adding 40% activated carbon had the best-promoting effect on copyrolysis, reducing the oxygen-containing compounds by 45.62% in bio-oil	76
Chlorella vulgaris PP	4:1	microwave 800 W, N ₂ 150 mL·min ⁻¹ , catalysts: graphite/Al ₂ O ₃	the addition of layered additives (e.g., graphite + Al ₂ O ₃) shortened the time required to reach the maximum mass-loss rate and significantly increased bio-oil yield	88
fresh water algae PP, PE, EPS	1:1	microwave 450 W, 600 °C, ~50–60 °C·min ⁻¹ , catalyst: ZSM5	catalytic copyrolysis led to a marked reduction in both the viscosity and density of the resulting bio-oil. The synergistic interactions between plastic and biomass during the process were clearly reflected in the properties and chemical composition of the produced oil	85

reactions, generating hydrogen. This interaction hampers bio-oil formation, thereby boosting gas production.⁶⁴ The large-scale molecular structures of polymers undergo fragmentation into smaller molecules or oligomers, which can further decompose into monomeric units. The further breakdown of these molecules is affected by several parameters, including reaction temperature, residence time, the presence of catalysts, and other operational conditions. The resulting liquid product from plastic pyrolysis holds a comparable calorific value to conventional fuels, typically around 40 MJ kg⁻¹.²³ In recent years, growing interest has emerged in research focused on the copyrolysis of different biomass types with plastics, driven by its potential to improve both the yield and quality of bio-oil, as well as to enhance the characteristics of the resulting char.⁶⁵ Vo et al.⁶⁵ and numerous other researchers have also acknowledged the potential of polymers in mixtures with different kinds of biomass during the copyrolysis process.^{66–68}

3.2. Particle Size

Biomass pretreatment techniques frequently involve reducing the size and compacting the biomass. These methods aim to enhance the material's bulk density and energy density, resulting in more cost-effective transportation, particularly when handling large quantities of biomass. However, it is essential to note that thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) experiments typically require feedstock samples in milligram (mg) quantities, indicating that the particle size of the feedstock must be relatively small. According to the existing literature, the size of biomass particles primarily affects the process kinetics. The particle size of the feedstock and the heating rate are key factors that directly influence both the pyrolysis kinetics and the overall energy requirements of the process.³⁶ Minimizing particle size is essential to enhance reaction efficiency and facilitate biofuel production via surface-driven reactions. For effective fast pyrolysis, biomass should be thoroughly dried to a moisture content of below 10 wt % and ground into particles smaller than 1 mm. Flash pyrolysis, which demands even more rapid heat transfer, typically requires particle sizes below 0.2 mm to attain the necessary high heating rates.²⁷

Wu et al.⁶⁹ investigated the impact of plastic particle size on the copyrolysis of *Dunaliella tertiolecta* and polypropylene (PP). Their study revealed that incorporating PP with smaller particle sizes led to a slight reduction in the maximum pyrolysis temperature of *D. tertiolecta* compared to its individual pyrolysis. These findings indicate that PP particles smaller than 125 μm can facilitate the thermal decomposition of *D. tertiolecta*, effectively lowering its peak pyrolytic temperature. In contrast, larger PP particles (about 1 mm) have minimal impact on *D. tertiolecta*'s maximum pyrolytic temperature. When the particle sizes of PP and *D. tertiolecta* are comparable, they can be blended more uniformly, enhancing the contact area. Pei et al.⁷⁰ noted that the residues from the coliquefaction of microalgae with plastic were enveloped in a waxy plastic layer. This observation suggests that improved microalgae coverage facilitates heat retention and bolsters the pyrolytic reaction.

Regardless of the feedstock ratio, larger particle size PP did not support the pyrolysis of *D. tertiolecta*, indicating that the particle size of raw materials or physical uniformity significantly affects their interaction.⁶⁹ According to the thermogravimetric analysis conducted in this literature, microalgae and polypropylene copyrolysis revealed a significant dependency on the

weight ratio of the components and the size of the polypropylene particles, which affects their interaction within the copyrolysis process. The researchers of Rasam et al.³⁸ also noted that PP may interact with carbon dioxide or carbonyl groups present in microalgae, reducing carbon dioxide production. In most copyrolysis research, particle sizes smaller than 1 mm were chosen to avoid internal heat or mass transfer effects. The size of the feedstock particles impacts not only the temperature and heating rate during the biomass pyrolysis assisted by microwaves but also the production of bio-oil resulting from the process. However, the correlation between the size of feedstock particles and bio-oil yield in biomass pyrolysis assisted by microwaves is inconsistent.⁵⁵

3.3. Blending Ratio

Co-pyrolysis differs from conventional pyrolysis in that it involves a unique parameter known as the feedstock ratio. This parameter is crucial as it significantly impacts liquid production.²³ Interactions with higher plastic ratios could be more assertive. A greater proportion of plastics in the initial raw materials increases hydrogen donation to the biomass. This interaction enhances the liquid yield, particularly when the plastic ratio in the mixture is higher.^{3,15,58} In fast catalytic copyrolysis scenarios, interactions generally reduce solid residue production (char and coke) due to the plastics, which enhance the H-to-C ratio (H/C_{eff}). The increased H/C_{eff} ratio can suppress the formation of oxygenated compounds from the biomass while promoting the generation of aromatics and alcohols.^{18,64} However, when biomass and PVC are used together in copyrolysis, a higher plastic ratio supports the creation of char, as the chlorine radicals found in PVC facilitate this process. As a result, this interaction enhances char production while reducing liquid formation.⁷¹

Additionally, as plastic melts, it can adhere to the surface of biomass, block the pores within the char produced from biomass, disrupt heat flow, restrain the release of volatile compounds, and consequently lead to an augmented formation of solid residue.¹⁹ An increased proportion of plastic can also promote gas production, as the volatile substances emitted by the plastic may undergo secondary reactions.⁶⁴ During its decomposition, biomass emits a multitude of radicals. Therefore, adjusting the ratio of biomass (or reducing the ratio of plastic) in the mixture can lead to an increased abundance of reactive radicals, thereby enhancing the disintegration of the plastic chain.⁶⁴ The ratio at which various raw materials are mixed can significantly influence the copyrolysis process and its results.²⁷ Table 5 presents a series of experiments conducted using different ratios during copyrolysis processes.

3.4. Temperature and Heating Rate

Both the pyrolysis temperature and the rate of heating play critical roles in determining the distribution and composition of the resulting products. Different temperature ranges can favor the formation of specific products. The heating rate and operating temperature have a significant impact on both the quantity and chemical composition of the products generated during pyrolysis. The rate at which heat is applied during pyrolysis plays a crucial role in shaping both the yield and the chemical profile of the resulting products. A faster heating rate to a moderate temperature tends to result in higher amounts of volatile compounds and liquid products. Conversely, a slower heating rate at the same temperature results in increased char

production. This demonstrates that the heating rate influences the distribution of different product types during pyrolysis.²⁵

Based on thermogravimetric studies, it has been observed that microalgae begin decomposing at a lower temperature (200 °C),⁷² whereas plastic materials exhibit decomposition in the temperature range of 350 and 550 °C,^{63,69} with variations contingent on the specific type of plastic (HDPE, LDPE, PS, and PP).⁶³ The initial phase of moisture elimination during plastic pyrolysis is absent, and most plastics undergo devolatilization in a single stage.³⁶ The decomposition rate for PVC is significantly lower than that of other plastics. The pyrolysis of PVC exhibits a distinct characteristic of two stages. Generally, the first stage occurs at around 250–350 °C, resulting in approximately 65% weight loss. The second thermal stage, occurring between 350 and 525 °C, is characterized by the cracking and breakdown of dehydrochlorinated PVC (polyvinyl chloride).⁷³

The pyrolysis of microalgae typically proceeds through three clearly defined stages, each of which is thermally reactive. During the first stage, which occurs up to 200 °C, the moisture present in the microalgae is eliminated, resulting in a mass loss. The degree of mass reduction in this phase is significantly affected by the initial moisture content of the microalgae feedstock.⁷⁴ The second phase, between 200 and 600 °C, represents the most reactive period and substantially contributes to the total mass reduction during pyrolysis. During this phase, all major microalgal constituents, including carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, and trace components, undergo thermal degradation. This decomposition results in the creation of char and the release of volatile substances.⁶⁹ The third stage begins around 600 °C and is characterized by a modest mass loss, primarily due to the decomposition of carbon-rich residues remaining in the solid phase. The most prominent peaks, corresponding to the main pyrolysis or devolatilization phase, are observed at approximately 320 °C, 290 °C, and 280 °C, respectively. These peaks are a consequence of the heat-induced breakdown of carbohydrates and proteins, with their thermal degradation peaks often overlapping. The smaller peaks accompanying the main ones result from the thermal decomposition of lipids, which necessitate higher temperatures for pyrolysis compared to carbohydrates and proteins.⁷⁴ Most studies have used temperatures up to 550 °C for microalgae pyrolysis, as shown in Table 2.

In the copyrolysis of plastics with microalgae, the presence of plastics has been shown to enhance the thermal degradation of microalgae and reduce the temperature necessary for their decomposition. For instance, during the copyrolysis of *Nannochloropsis* sp. (NS) with polypropylene (PP), the peak decomposition temperature of NS was marginally lower than that observed during its individual pyrolysis.⁴⁸ In copyrolysis, the 400–600 °C temperature range is generally optimal for maximizing oil production.³⁸ From the work of Qi et al.,⁴⁸ it was observed that increasing the copyrolysis temperature of *Nannochloropsis* sp. (NS) and polypropylene (PP) from 500 to 900 °C led to a gradual decline in the yields of bio-oil and biochar, while the production of gaseous products increased markedly.

3.5. Application of Catalysts

Catalytic copyrolysis presents a promising approach for upgrading biomass into high-quality bio-oil with improved chemical characteristics; however, several crucial consider-

ations warrant attention for future research endeavors. One of these factors is the acidity of the catalyst used in the process. While high acidity can promote deoxygenation and the production of aromatics and olefins, it can also lead to excessive coke formation. Thus, the acidity of the catalyst must be carefully optimized during the design phase to achieve maximal yields of desired products while minimizing coke formation. This can be done by adjusting the Si/Al ratio to control acidity.⁶²

Apart from zeolites and metal oxides, various materials or combinations thereof are utilized as in situ catalysts in MAP processes for diverse feedstocks.⁷⁵ Microwave-assisted catalytic pyrolysis combines the advantages of catalytic pyrolysis and microwave heating to achieve high conversion rates and selective production of aromatic compounds. In microwave-assisted catalytic pyrolysis, a suitable catalyst that can function as both a microwave receptor and a catalyst is crucial. This is because microwave heating is a selective and efficient method of heating materials that contain polar functional groups, such as water and oxygen-containing compounds, but is less effective in heating nonpolar compounds, such as hydrocarbons.²⁶

Carbon-based materials are particularly suitable as catalysts in these processes because they can serve as catalysts and microwave absorbers.⁷⁵ Both *Chlorella vulgaris* (CV) and PP have a limited ability to absorb microwaves, necessitating the use of microwave absorbents in the experiment to enhance the efficiency of pyrolysis and increase the yield of products.⁷⁶ Chen et al.⁷⁶ studied the impact of varying amounts of graphite (GP) additions (from 10% to 40%) on the optimal blend ratio of CV/PP 8:2 (referred to as C8P2 mixture). The C8P2 blend supplemented with 30% GP exhibited the highest values for both the maximum weight loss rate and the average weight loss rate. In the absence of GP, the C8P2 mixture displayed a 21.58% decrease in N compound content in the oil compared to the C10P0 mixture. When GP was added to the C8P2 mixture, the 30% GP mixture bio-oil exhibited N compound levels that were 1.93% less than those of the 0% GP.

The study also investigated microwave-assisted copyrolysis of CV and HDPE, utilizing activated carbon (AC) as a microwave absorber to enhance heating efficiency. The outcomes indicated that the optimal mixing ratio was CV/HDPE = 1:1, and the inclusion of 40% AC significantly enhanced the copyrolysis attributes of the blend. Additionally, the inclusion of HDPE significantly increased the concentrations of hydrocarbons and alcohols in the resulting bio-oil. Simultaneously, nitrogen-containing compounds were reduced by 75.75% relative to pure CV, a reduction attributed to the enhanced formation of ammonia (NH₃) and hydrogen cyanide (HCN). The introduction of 40% AC to the blend resulted in a 48.88% increase in hydrocarbons within the bio-oil and a 45.62% decrease in oxygen-containing compounds compared to the PC group, facilitating the creation of H₂O, CO, and CO₂. Overall, the incorporation of HDPE and activated carbon (AC) enhanced the pyrolysis performance of CV, while also exhibiting beneficial effects on the denitrification and deoxygenation of the resulting bio-oil.⁷⁷

Qi et al.⁴⁸ explored the catalytic copyrolysis of *Nannochloropsis* sp. (NS) and polypropylene (PP) in a fixed-bed reactor, employing HZSM-5 zeolite as the catalyst. The primary objective of the study was to enhance the selective and efficient generation of aromatic hydrocarbons. The introduction of catalysts had a notable influence on the yields

of products, with gas yields increasing and char yields initially decreasing before growing again. At a feedstock-to-catalyst mass ratio of 1:3, the study observed a minimum char yield of 9%. As the catalyst dosage increased, the catalytic cracking activity intensified, promoting greater formation of gaseous products. However, excessive catalyst loading resulted in a reduction in bio-oil yield, primarily due to secondary cracking of pyrolysis vapors as they passed through the HZSM-5 zeolite catalyst bed. The study found that the composition of oils from copyrolysis varied depending on the feedstock/catalyst ratio. In the absence of a catalyst, copyrolysis produced bio-oil with a low concentration of aromatic hydrocarbons and a high proportion of nitrogen-containing compounds, which can hinder downstream upgrading and application. However, the introduction of HZSM-5 zeolite significantly enhanced aromatic hydrocarbon content, from 43.38% to 93.29%, while substantially reducing olefins from 33.19% to 2.29%. Additionally, nitrogenous compounds were reduced from 18.37% to 0.59% as the mass ratio of NS to PP/HZSM-5 increased from 1:0 to 1:10. This improvement is attributed to the ability of HZSM-5 to effectively expose pyrolysis vapors to its catalytic surface, allowing for the formation of intermediate polar products through degradation reactions. This process destroyed and removed nitrogen-containing functional groups, resulting in an increase in hydrocarbons and nonpolar compounds, thereby reducing the nitrogen compound content in the oil. Overall, the use of HZSM-5 as a catalyst significantly improves the quality of bio-oil obtained from the copyrolysis of *Nannochloropsis* sp. (NS) and polypropylene (PP).

Gao et al.⁷⁸ study the effects of catalysts such as calcium oxide (CaO) and ZSM-5 during the copyrolysis process of CV and PP. They compared the kinetic parameters and product distribution of the copyrolysis using both theoretical and experimental approaches to gain a better understanding of the roles of the two catalysts. The results revealed that the weight loss rates in catalytic copyrolysis were lowest in the noncatalytic process, followed by CaO and ZSM-5 catalysts. CaO contributed to the increased activation energy, while ZSM-5 had the contrary effect. Both catalysts caused a reduction in the O- and N-containing groups within the pyrolysis product, with CaO showing a higher effectiveness in removing oxygen. In comparison, ZSM-5 showed a higher effectiveness in removing nitrogen. ZSM-5 facilitated a selective increase in aromatic hydrocarbon production, raising their proportion from 12.23% to 14.56%, whereas CaO favored the generation of aliphatic hydrocarbons, increasing their content from 70.67% to 80.95%.

Catalysts employed in catalytic copyrolysis, including acidic zeolites, metal oxides, and highly porous materials, often undergo rapid deactivation. A predominant deactivation mechanism is the deposition of carbonaceous coke, which covers active acidic sites and inhibits reactant access.⁷⁹ In parallel, agglomeration and sintering of metal particles can occur, leading to a loss of dispersion and catalytic activity. For catalysts containing supported metals (e.g., Ni- or Fe-based systems), changes in the metal oxidation state induced by the reactor atmosphere may further affect catalytic performance. These deactivation pathways significantly limit catalyst lifetime, highlighting the need for improved catalyst design and regeneration strategies in catalytic copyrolysis systems.⁸⁰

For deactivation mechanisms, elevated temperatures combined with hydrogen-deficient conditions promote catalyst coking, whereby carbonaceous deposits block pores and acidic

active sites.⁷⁹ The deposited carbon can evolve into dense, graphitic (“hard coke”) structures as well as weaker-bound surface (“soft”) coke species. Simultaneously, metal particles may undergo sintering, particularly in Ni- or Fe-based catalysts, which reduces the number of exposed active sites.⁸⁰ In addition, changes in metal oxidation states may occur as a result of interactions with oxidizing agents or reactive gas-phase species, leading to partial catalyst deactivation (e.g., via partial oxidation of metallic particles).⁴⁷

Considering regeneration strategies, coke removal is commonly achieved by oxidative regeneration (controlled combustion) or by thermal treatment under an inert atmosphere. Oxidative regeneration in air or steam can effectively restore pore accessibility and acidic active sites, as oxygen lowers the activation energy for coke degradation.⁷⁹ However, excessively high regeneration temperatures may irreversibly damage zeolite frameworks or induce sintering of residual metal particles. Another frequently applied approach is reimpregnation, in which fresh metal species are deposited onto the regenerated support. Nevertheless, regeneration is often accompanied by partial losses in surface area and catalytic activity; for example, fluid catalytic cracking (FCC) catalysts are known to lose a fraction of their acidic active sites after multiple regeneration cycles. Moreover, regeneration procedures are energetically demanding, which further constrains catalyst lifetime and overall process efficiency.¹⁷

In economic aspects, catalyst-related costs are a significant factor in scaling up copyrolysis technologies. Numerous studies indicate that catalyst prices and associated operating costs are among the most significant economic parameters of the overall process.⁸¹ Sensitivity analyses further demonstrate that, even under industrial operating conditions, high catalyst costs or frequent regeneration requirements can substantially increase the cost per unit of produced fuel. Consequently, there is growing interest in low-cost catalyst alternatives, including inexpensive catalyst blends and waste-derived materials such as red mud or spent FCC catalysts, as well as in optimizing regeneration procedures to maximize catalyst lifetime and reuse.¹⁷

As far as active sites and reaction mechanisms are concerned, acidic sites typical of zeolites (such as H-ZSM-5 and HY) promote the scission of C–C bonds and the aromatization of pyrolysis intermediates, leading to an increased formation of aromatic compounds and light hydrocarbons. In contrast, basic catalysts (e.g., MgO, CaO, and other metal oxides) primarily catalyze decarboxylation and deamination reactions, thereby facilitating the removal of carboxyl (–COOH) and amino functional groups originating from biomass decomposition. For instance, CaO effectively removes carboxylic acids, converts oxygen into CO₂ and H₂O, and neutralizes acidic species.⁸¹ Metallic catalysts (e.g., Fe-, Ni-, or Co-based systems) additionally enable hydrogenation-related reactions. Under hydrogen-rich conditions derived from biomass decomposition or water–gas reactions hydrodeoxygenation and denitrification pathways may prevail, whereas in the absence of external hydrogen supply, radical-mediated hydrogen transfer reactions become dominant.²⁴

3.6. Summary

Co-pyrolysis of microalgae and plastic waste is carried out in an oxygen-free reactor and involves the simultaneous thermal decomposition of multiple feedstocks, leveraging synergistic interactions to yield a more even distribution of products than

in single-feed pyrolysis. Numerous operational factors, including reactor temperature, heating rate, particle size, residence time, and the use of catalysts or hydrogen donors, can influence process outcomes, but feedstock characteristics and their blending ratios are particularly critical parameters. The unique compositions of the feedstocks strongly affect copyrolysis behavior: microalgal biomass typically contains high moisture and oxygen (due to carbohydrates/proteins), leading to lower-quality bio-oil, whereas waste plastics consist of hydrogen-rich hydrocarbons with negligible oxygen. When copyrolyzed, the plastics can donate hydrogen and dilute oxygen-rich components from the biomass, enhancing hydrocarbon formation and suppressing unwanted oxygenated/nitrogenated compounds in the bio-oil. As a result, higher plastic proportions in the feed generally increase liquid oil yield and energy content while reducing char production. Proper feedstock preparation (e.g., drying biomass and fine milling) further improves efficiency, though drying is energy-intensive; adding dry plastics lowers the overall water content of the produced oil. In practice, optimizing these experimental conditions (feed blend ratios, particle size, etc.) is vital to achieve favorable synergy; under the right conditions, copyrolysis yields more liquid fuel and valuable coproducts, thereby enhancing process performance and economic viability over conventional single-feed pyrolysis.

4. INFLUENCE OF OPERATING CONDITIONS ON THE YIELD AND QUALITY OF COPYROLYSIS PRODUCTS

4.1. Co-Pyrolysis Products Yields

During pyrolysis, feedstock materials are thermochemically transformed into three primary product phases: noncondensable gas, liquid bio-oil, and solid char. Char, liquid, and gas yields from microalgal-plastics copyrolysis using 1:1 mixing ratio are demonstrated in Table 6. Bio-oil constituted approximately 50% of the total product yield, which aligns with its high content of fat and protein.⁷¹ The pyrolysis of individual plastic materials yielded a more significant oil fraction, ranging from 55% to 82.34% by weight, a non-condensable fraction between 13.84% and 27% by weight, and a minor char fraction of 0% to 6% by weight.^{3,65,82} As shown in Figure 1, the pyrolysis process is dominated by the production of oil at the expense of gaseous and solid components.

In comparison, pyrolysis of PVC produced a gas yield of 67.6% and the lowest liquid yield at 14.42%. These results are attributed to PVC's relatively high ash and fixed carbon content, its lower volatile matter fraction, and the occurrence of dehydrochlorination during thermal degradation.⁸⁴ The assessment of copyrolysis product yields relies heavily on the mixing ratios of the single fuels.⁵⁸ According to Kumar et al.,⁵⁸ *Nannochloropsis* sp. pyrolysis produced 52.26 wt % of oil, with 17.79 wt % of gases and 29.95 wt % of solid fractions. The inclusion of PS in the mixtures significantly affected the distribution of pyrolysis products, particularly in the liquid yield. As anticipated based on theoretical values, this effect was more pronounced at higher PS contents, specifically at 35% and 50% by weight, resulting in liquid yields exceeding 60% by weight. When the PS percentage in the blends reached 75%, the liquid yield increased substantially by 42.70% compared to *Nannochloropsis* sp. pyrolysis alone. As a result, the percentages of noncondensable gases and char decreased proportionally.⁵⁸

Table 6. Char, Liquid, and Gas Yield from Microalgal-Plastics Co-Pyrolysis Using a 1:1 Mixing Ratio^a

plastics	feedstocks	co-pyrolysis parameters				gas flow rate	char yield (wt %)		liquid yield (wt %)		gas yield (wt %)		refs
		microalgae	pyrolysis mode	temperature/power	microalgae		mix	microalgae	mix	microalgae	mix		
PVC	Chlorella vulgaris	microwave-assisted fast pyrolysis	800 W	N ₂ 300 mL·min ⁻¹	29.66	~38	44.42	~24	26	38	71		
LDPE	Nannochloropsis sp	conventional pyrolysis	600 °C	Ar 150 mL·min ⁻¹	19.53	~9	65.17	~73	~15	~18	15		
PP	Nannochloropsis sp	catalytic pyrolysis	800 °C	Ar 200 mL·min ⁻¹	~23	~11	~38	~45	~39	~44	48		
PS	Chlorella sorokiniana	conventional pyrolysis	500 °C	Ar	31.05	19.89	43.23	70.15	~26	9.85	60		
PS	Nannochloropsis sp	conventional pyrolysis	500 °C	Ar 150 mL·min ⁻¹	29.95	17.89	52.26	68.84	17.79	13.27	58		
HDPE	Chlorella vulgaris	microwave-assisted fast pyrolysis	800 W	N ₂ 700 mL·min ⁻¹	-	11.74	-	18.15	-	70.11	86		
PP	freshwater algae	microwave-assisted in situ catalytic pyrolysis	600 °C	-	~19	~12	~46	~45	~35	~43	85		
PE	freshwater algae	microwave-assisted in situ catalytic pyrolysis	600 °C	-	~19	~13	~46	~37	~35	49.5	85		
EPS	freshwater algae	microwave-assisted in situ catalytic pyrolysis	600 °C	-	~19	~12	~46	~65	~35	22.5	85		
PP	Chlorella vulgaris	microwave-assisted pyrolysis	800 W	N ₂ 150 mL·min ⁻¹	27.05	12.06	12.47	10.47	60.48	77.47	76		

^aNot reported; ~calculated from data in the article or estimated from the figure (not stated directly in the article).

During copyrolysis of *Nannochloropsis* sp. and polypropylene (PP) at 800 °C, the bio-oil yield progressively increased as the mass ratio of microalgae to PP shifted from 3:1 to 1:1. The peak oil yield of 45% was achieved at a 1:1 ratio. However, increasing the proportion of PP led to the formation of numerous small molecules from PP pyrolysis, promoting a secondary cracking reaction. As a result, the oil and char underwent conversion into smaller molecules that were released to the gas.⁴⁸ For the copyrolysis of *Nannochloropsis* sp. and LDPE, the amount of liquid oil obtained increased in direct proportion to the LDPE content, while the production of char decreased gradually. This can be attributed to LDPE containing a high percentage of volatile components (over 80%), which undergo cracking into liquid and gas forms during pyrolysis. The experimental gas yield consistently exceeds the theoretical value, while the liquid output falls short of expectations. However, there's no notable difference in the char yield. This trend is attributed to the copyrolysis process facilitating the secondary cracking of heavier volatile compounds into lighter gaseous molecules, thereby increasing gas production. The synergistic interaction was most pronounced at a microalgae-to-LDPE mass ratio of 3:1.¹⁵

A study examining the thermal behavior of copyrolyzing *Dunaliella salina* (DS) with various plastics, including polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), and polyethylene terephthalate (PET), reported a reduction in the amount of solid residue produced from the blends. This reduction was attributed to hydrogenation reactions between the unsaturated compounds from biomass and plastics. Conversely, copyrolysis of DS with PVC resulted in a 1.36 wt % increase in solid residue, likely attributed to both physical and chemical interactions occurring between the components during thermal decomposition.¹⁹

Suriapparao et al.⁸⁵ conducted binary copyrolysis experiments to evaluate the combined effects of fresh algae (FA) with synthetic polymers, including polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and expanded polystyrene (EPS). Using a 1:1 mass ratio and operating at 450 W, the study found that the FA + EPS combination produced the highest bio-oil yield at approximately 65 wt %, followed by FA + PP at around 45 wt %, and FA + PE yielding roughly 40 wt %. The copyrolysis of FA with both PE and PP resulted in lower-than-expected oil yields, suggesting that these combinations may inhibit bio-oil formation rather than enhance it. However, both combinations exhibited higher gas yields, suggesting a beneficial synergy in gas production. In contrast, FA + EPS combinations demonstrated higher oil yields. This behavior may be attributed to interactions among vapor-phase components in the FA + PE and FA + PP blends, where deoxygenation reactions play a dominant role. The volatile oxygenated compounds from FA likely reacted preferentially with volatile hydrocarbons from PE or PP to form CO₂ and H₂O, rather than interacting with the aromatic volatiles from EPS. As a result, the FA + PE and FA + PP combinations produced lower bio-oil yields and higher gas outputs, whereas the FA + EPS system demonstrated the opposite trend, favoring bio-oil formation.

Several researchers (Chen et al.,^{76,86} Dai et al.,⁷¹ Kumar et al.,⁶⁰ and Majid et al.⁸⁷) investigated the copyrolysis of microalgae strain *Chlorella* with plastics. Dai et al.⁷¹ studied the copyrolysis of *Chlorella vulgaris* (MA) and PVC. It was observed that at power levels of 800 and 1000 W, the product distribution shifted with varying MA proportions. As the MA

content decreased, the char yield initially increased from 42.4% to 43.3% at a 7:3 ratio, then progressively declined, reaching a minimum of 19.3%. Simultaneously, the oil yield declined from 37.7% to 23.0%, while the gas yield increased substantially from 19.8% to 57.6%. This shift aligned with expectations, as MA produced fewer gaseous products, whereas PVC tended to generate higher liquid yields during pyrolysis. It is noteworthy that at blend ratios of 9:1 and 7:3, the char yield was considerably higher than in the other formulations, indicating a pronounced interaction that promoted char formation. Additionally, increasing the microwave power from 800 to 1000 W resulted in a noticeable increase in both gas and liquid yields, accompanied by a corresponding decrease in solid residue, although the extent of this decrease varied across samples. This could be attributed to the heightened heating rate, which promoted chemical bond cracking and facilitated the release of pyrolysis vapors. With a reduction in the proportion of MA, both char and bio-oil yields initially increased, peaking at 41.5% at a 7:3 blend ratio, before gradually declining to 24.9%. In contrast, gas yield first dropped from 28.2% to 24.9% at the same ratio, then rose sharply to 61.9%. Notably, carbohydrates displayed a negligible catalytic influence on the release of hydrogen chloride (HCl) during the pyrolysis process.⁷¹

Chen et al.^{76,88} and Gao et al.⁷⁸ studied *Chlorella vulgaris* (CV) with PP. Investigated how varying the mixing ratios of CV and polypropylene (PP) influenced the distribution of products generated through copyrolysis. When the polypropylene (PP) content increased, the solid product yield decreased. This decrease can be attributed to the significantly lower solid yield from PP pyrolysis compared to CV pyrolysis. The cracking of hydrogen atoms by PP during pyrolysis accelerated the cracking of substances in CV, resulting in a decrease in solid yield during the pyrolysis process. Consequently, there was an increase in the yield of gas or bio-oil as the solid yield decreased. Specifically, in the C2P8 mixture, the solid product yield was 5.66%, the gas yield was 83.91%, and the oil yield was 10.43%. This result was likely attributed to secondary cracking reactions that occurred during pyrolysis, in which pyrolysis vapors were further broken down into lighter organic compounds or noncondensable gases, leading to an increase in gas yield. However, this process also caused a slight reduction in the overall bio-oil yield. The optimal mixing ratio was found in the C8P2 mixture, where the bio-oil yield peaked at 14.03%, the solid yield at 20.71%, and the gas yield at 65.26%.

The copyrolysis of CV with HDPE was mentioned in the work of Chen et al.^{77,86} and Majid et al.⁸⁷ Chen et al.⁸⁶ reported that a 1:1 mixing ratio of CV and PP (C1HP1) produced 11.74% solid residue, 18.15% bio-oil, and 70.11% gaseous products. Additionally, the use of CE/AC catalysts enhanced gas production while lowering the amount of solid residue. In contrast, the application of Fe/AC and Ni/AC catalysts resulted in increased solid residue yields and a corresponding decline in gas output.

4.2. Effect on Bio-Oil Quality

The primary and financially advantageous result of copyrolysis is the liquid fraction, which has the largest volume and exhibits the most significant potential for commercial utilization.⁸⁹

4.2.1. Water Concentration and pH. Tang et al.¹⁵ examined the liquid derived from *Nannochloropsis* sp. (NA) and found it to have a moisture content of 12.84 wt %. Upon adding LDPE, the moisture content remained relatively stable

up to 33% LDPE content, but it decreased as the LDPE content was more increased. It is worth noting that the measured moisture content consistently surpassed the theoretical values, which suggests that copyrolysis encouraged the conversion of oxygen-containing groups into H₂O.

The oil's pH level is vital for assessing potential corrosion risks. The pyrolysis oil derived from *Nannochloropsis* (NA) displayed a mildly alkaline pH of approximately 10. While this alkalinity may seem moderate, it raises potential concerns regarding the corrosiveness of the oil, particularly in transport systems. In contrast, pyrolysis oil produced from LDPE exhibited a near-neutral pH of around 7. As the proportion of LDPE increased in the copyrolysis process, the pH of the resulting liquid product gradually decreased. This phenomenon could be attributed to the dissolution of some NH₃ produced from protein pyrolysis into the oil.¹⁵ The pH values of the bio-oils obtained from CSR and PS ranged from 4.61 to 6.40. Following copyrolysis, the pH values ranged from 5.65.⁶⁰ By adding plastics, Kumar et al.⁶⁰ also examined slightly decreasing pH values. This trend indicates a progressive stabilization of the oil and reduced corrosivity, which is favorable for downstream upgrading.

4.2.2. Elemental Analysis Results and Heating Value of Bio-Oil. The copyrolysis process increases the amount of oil generated and enhances its quality by boosting its high calorific value. Synthetic plastics, primarily organic polymers obtained from petroleum products, contain substantial amounts of carbon and hydrogen, minimal or no oxygen, and exhibit a comparable high heating value (HHV) to traditional fossil fuels.²² Dai et al.⁷¹ reported that blending CV with PVC improved the heating value of the resulting pyrolysis oil, increasing it from 33.05 MJ kg⁻¹ to 39.73 MJ kg⁻¹, especially at higher PVC proportions. However, when the microwave power was raised to 1000 W, the heating value generally declined compared to that observed at 800 W, except in the case of the 3:7 CV to PVC ratio. This suggests that higher microwave power has an inhibitory effect on CV and PVC; consequently, it is unfavorable for the heating value of the oil.

According to Kumar et al.,⁵⁸ incorporating PS into the blends with *Nannochloropsis* sp. decreased nitrogen and oxygen contents in the organic phase and raised the carbon content, thereby leading to a higher heating value. Suriapparao et al.⁸⁵ analyzed the elemental composition of pyrolysis oils produced from blends of fresh algae (FA) with PE, PP, and EPS. The results revealed variations in carbon, hydrogen, and oxygen content across the samples, with the FA + EPS combination exhibiting the highest carbon content at 90%, followed by FA + PP at 85%, and FA + PE at 82%. FA + PE showed a relatively high oxygen content, while FA + PP had a higher hydrogen content. Nevertheless, despite these differences in C, H, and O contents, they did not notably affect the higher heating value (HHV) of the pyrolysis products. The measured HHV values for all combinations were approximately 42 ± 1 MJ kg⁻¹. Additionally, the addition of plastic during pyrolysis had varying effects on nitrogen (N) yields, depending on the type of algae. In the case of copyrolysis of *Spirulina platensis* (SP) and LDPE resulted in a slight decrease in the N yield of the pyrolytic oil (from 19.5 wt % to 6.6 wt %), while the N content in the gas phase increased. Conversely, for *Nannochloropsis* sp. (NA), copyrolysis increased the oil's nitrogen yield but decreased the N yields of the gas and char phases.³¹ The

bio-oil from CSR/PS copyrolysis was characterized by a heating value of 39.37 MJ kg⁻¹.⁶⁰

4.2.3. Chemical Components. The fluid substances obtained from the pyrolysis process comprise a diverse array of organic compounds. These products are categorized into several groups: aliphatic hydrocarbons, aromatic hydrocarbons, oxygenated compounds, nitrogenated compounds, and other miscellaneous compounds. Dai et al.⁷¹ examined the presence of PVC, which significantly impacted the chemical composition of the fluid products. With the diminishing proportion of *Chlorella vulgaris*, there was a decline in aliphatic hydrocarbons and a simultaneous increase in aromatic hydrocarbons, rising from 29.58% to 92.71%. Nevertheless, the overall hydrocarbon content increased from 51.5% to 99.4%, accompanied by a decrease in nitrogen content from 29.7% to 0.38%. At mixing ratios of 9:1 and 7:3, a few phenols and ketones were still present, but their concentrations decreased sharply with the rising PVC content.⁷¹ After mixing LDPE with *Nannochloropsis* sp. (NA), there was a significant increase in the abundance of aliphatic hydrocarbons.¹⁵

Similar results were reported by Tang et al.³¹ LDPE positively influenced the production of long-chain alcohols and formic/acetic esters during pyrolysis. The copyrolysis of *Chlorella* solid residue (ChSR) with PP showed that the hydrocarbon content increased significantly, even with a small amount of PP added. Moreover, the relative proportions of hydrocarbons increased with the rising PP addition ratio. The hydrocarbon products from the 80% ChSR and 20% PP mixture included many cyclohexane derivatives. Cyclization of these chain hydrocarbons with the free radicals formed significant cyclohexane derivatives. The presence of nitrogen-containing compounds declined (from 13.86% to 2.67%), as also expected in the 80%ChSR20%PP blend.¹²

Kumar et al.⁶⁰ examined the inclusion of PS led to a decrease in the proportion of O compounds (including aldehydes, acids, phenols, and ketones) from 30% to 1%. Similarly, the N compounds (such as amides, nitriles, and indoles) decreased from 16% to 1%. This could be attributed to the inhibitory effect of free radicals, which hindered the interaction between amino acids, resulting from protein degradation, and long-chain aliphatic acids, leading to a decline in the formation of amides. The incorporation of 25% PS led to a substantial rise in the volume of aromatic hydrocarbons, rising from 16.22% to 71.44%. The enhanced synthesis of aromatic hydrocarbons and the reduction in nitrogenated and oxygenated compounds could be attributed to the inherent chemical structure of PS.⁵⁸

According to the work of Chen et al.,⁸⁶ bio-oil from copyrolysis of *Chlorella vulgaris* with HDPE was primarily characterized by a higher proportion of aliphatic hydrocarbons, constituting 35.59% of the total. In contrast, the volume of aromatic hydrocarbons was only 2.29%. This could be attributed to the molecular structure of HDPE, which lacked branched chains and predominantly underwent straight chain cleavage during copyrolysis with *C. vulgaris*. As a result, the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons was hindered in this process. Chen et al.⁷⁷ investigated the characteristics of HDPE in copyrolysis and found that it exhibited strong denitration and deoxygenation effects on the resulting bio-oil. HDPE promoted the formation of long-chain alcohols and hydrocarbons, while simultaneously suppressing the production of amines and ketones. This effect was attributed to the release of hydrogen radicals from HDPE, which facilitated hydroxyl

Figure 2. Effect on biochar quality after copyrolysis of *Chlorella vulgaris* and PVC.

group formation and subsequently enhanced the synthesis of long-chain alcohols.

Suriapparao et al.⁸⁵ identified that the primary functional groups in FA + PP bio-oil were aliphatic hydrocarbons, accounting for approximately 70% of the composition. This was followed by cyclic aliphatic hydrocarbons, making up approximately 10%, and polyaromatic hydrocarbons, accounting for approximately 10%.

In summary, although experimental conditions differ widely among studies, the underlying chemical trends are coherent: copyrolysis effectively converts low-value, oxygen- and nitrogen-rich algal bio-oil precursors into a hydrocarbon-rich, higher-calorific liquid fuel. The remaining variations in reported yields can be primarily attributed to the type of polymer, heating method, and catalyst acidity.

The products of microalgae-plastic copyrolysis can be utilized in a manner analogous to conventional pyrolytic fractions, although the mixed feedstock significantly alters their properties. Bio-oil obtained from copyrolysis typically contains fewer heteroatoms and oxygen-containing functional groups and exhibits a higher relative hydrogen content than oil derived from pure biomass.⁹⁰ These characteristics translate into higher calorific value and improved stability. The primary application of copyrolysis bio-oil is as a fuel, following appropriate upgrading either through direct combustion or as a blending component in biofuels (e.g., as an additive to diesel or as a feedstock for refinery processing). In addition, bio-oil can be hydrocracked or reformed to produce high-quality diesel-range hydrocarbons or aromatic compounds suitable for the chemical industry. Microalgae-derived copyrolysis oils generally exhibit lower nitrogen and oxygen contents (present, for example, in the form of amines, pyrroles, or furans) and therefore a higher H/C ratio, which facilitates their utilization as hydrocarbon-rich feedstocks.¹⁵

4.2.4. Miscibility and Aging of Bio-Oil. In addition to yield, pH, and water content, the oxidative stability and resistance to aging are key quality parameters of microalgae-derived bio-oil. Bio-oil produced via the pyrolytic conversion

of microalgae typically exhibits limited stability due to its high heteroatom content, particularly oxygen and nitrogen originating from polysaccharides, lipids, and proteins, which results in high corrosivity, elevated viscosity, and poor storage stability.²⁹ Oxygenated compounds (e.g., ketones, acids, phenols) and nitrogen heterocycles promote spontaneous polymerization during aging, increasing molecular weight, viscosity, acidity, and risking phase separation.⁹¹

Co-pyrolysis with polyolefin plastics (e.g., LDPE, PS, PP) markedly improves these properties through plastic cracking-supplied H-radicals, enabling in situ hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) and hydrogenation. This reduces O/C ratios (<15 wt % oxygen), minimizes N-compounds (converting to gases), and enriches hydrocarbons/aromatics (up to ~93% aliphatic compounds from PP),⁹² yielding a homogeneous, hydrophobic bio-oil. Consequently, it exhibits enhanced miscibility with fossil fuels (improved polarity enables >90% blending stability), suppressed deposit formation, and reduced polymerization/aqueous-organic phase separation.^{91,92}

Overall, the incorporation of polyolefin plastics into the pyrolysis of microalgae yields a bio-oil with enhanced oxidative stability and an extended storage lifetime. Due to its reduced oxygen content and lower abundance of unsaturated compounds, this oil is less prone to degradation during storage and more closely resembles standard fuels in terms of energy density and nonpolar character.^{29,92}

4.3. Effect on Biochar Quality

Co-pyrolysis has a significant effect on the physicochemical properties of both biochar and synthetic gas, primarily through the redistribution of carbon and hydrogen between the solid and volatile phases.

4.3.1. Elemental and Analysis and Heating Value of Biochar. Under copyrolysis of *Chlorella vulgaris* (CV) and PVC at 800 W, the carbon content experienced enrichment, rising from 62.77% to 82.54% with the addition of PVC. The mixture exhibited a higher oxygen content than the two samples, particularly at the 9:1 ratio. This suggests that the incomplete nature of the initial pyrolysis phase was due to

complex interactions between CV and PVC, hindering oxygen removal. As shown in Figure 2, the heating value of the resulting biochar increased from 23 MJ kg⁻¹ to 30 MJ kg⁻¹ with a higher PVC content. This improvement is primarily attributed to an increase in carbon concentration and a corresponding decrease in oxygen content within the char. The hydrogen content experienced a significant decrease, accompanied by a decrease in the H/C ratio, resulting in a decline in the heating value. Therefore, a power level of 1000 W was unfavorable for the char's heating value.⁷¹ In the process of copyrolysis *Nannochloropsis* sp. (NA) with low-density polyethylene, the composition of carbon, nitrogen, oxygen, and hydrogen within the copyrolysis chars showed a gradual reduction as the LDPE content increased. This observation suggested the possibility of an interaction occurring between the char and LDPE, which facilitated the pyrolysis of NA tar and consequently led to an increased production of volatile substances. The oxygen in NA tended to transform into H₂O and CO rather than CO₂. Additionally, the nitrogen content in NA was apparent that it would be released into the resulting gas products.¹⁵

4.3.2. Surface Morphology and Particle Size. The copyrolysis process of LDPE and *Nannochloropsis* sp. (NA) involved the melted LDPE wrapping around NA particles, effectively retaining the volatiles released during NA pyrolysis at elevated temperatures for an extended period. This prolonged exposure to high temperatures intensified secondary reactions. The morphology of the resulting char supported this inference. In the case of NA pyrolysis alone, the charcoal exhibited a smooth and even morphology without blowholes. This smoothness was attributed to the destruction and melting of the spherical cell wall structures at high temperatures. In contrast, the char surface became uneven with the addition of LDPE, and the cross-section revealed numerous blowholes. This observation indicated that including LDPE facilitated the pyrolysis of NS and the creation of pores. The presence of blowholes and irregularities in the char structure was likely due to the interaction between radicals generated from LDPE pyrolysis and the NA char, which destroyed the char structure.¹⁵ Suriapparao et al.⁸⁵ observed that the surface areas of the char samples from FA and EPS were comparable, indicating similar surface area levels. On the other hand, the char samples from PE and PP exhibited relatively higher surface areas than FA and EPS. The copyrolysis chars exhibited comparable surface areas, regardless of the specific combinations. The collaborative effect of copyrolysis facilitated the production of deoxygenated bio-oils with enhanced energy density. This phenomenon could be attributed to hydrogen transfer between the plastics and the bio-oil during the pyrolysis reactions.⁸⁵

In short, pyrolysis systematically redistributes elements among products: hydrogen from plastics enhances the calorific value of the gas and the quality of the liquid fuel, while carbon enrichment increases the energy density of the coal. The differences observed between studies reflect the type of plastic, the mixture ratio, and the heating regime rather than discrepancies in the basic reaction pathways.

The solid residue obtained after pyrolytic conversion exhibits applications comparable to those of conventional pyrolytic biochar. It can function as a soil conditioner and carbon-based fertilizer; in the case of microalgae-derived biochar, the high content of proteinaceous and mineral components results in elevated levels of nitrogen, phosphorus,

potassium, and other micro- and macronutrients. Consequently, the incorporation of algal biochar into soil can enhance nutrient availability and water retention, owing to its highly developed surface area and porous structure. Biochar also serves as an effective adsorbent for contaminants, including pesticides and heavy metals, making it suitable for the remediation of polluted soils and water bodies. Moreover, due to its porosity and chemical stability, biochar is frequently employed as a catalyst support (e.g., via impregnation with metals or zeolites) for subsequent thermochemical or electrochemical processes. Compared with lignocellulosic biochar (e.g., wood-derived biochar), microalgae-based biochar offers distinct advantages, including the absence of lignin and cellulose and an inherently higher nutrient content, which collectively enhance its agrochemical value.⁹³

4.4. Effect on Biogas Quality

Only some research dealt with or mentioned gaseous products and their calorific value in the works related to the copyrolysis of microalgae and plastics. During the pyrolysis process of *Nannochloropsis* sp., the primary gaseous products are CO₂, CO, CH₄, and higher hydrocarbons C₂₊. Tang et al.¹⁵ reported that the NS gas product's lower heating value (LHV) was measured at 23.56 MJ Nm³⁻. In contrast, the LHV of the pyrolysis gas from LDPE alone reached 60.91 MJ Nm³⁻. When *Nannochloropsis* sp. (NS) was copyrolyzed with LDPE, a significant increase in CO₂ concentration was observed compared to the pyrolysis of NS on its own. When the LDPE content increased, the CO₂ content decreased proportionally. The concentrations of CO and H₂ followed a similar trend. The copyrolysis process significantly enhanced the calorific value of the gaseous products, particularly with higher amounts of LDPE. The resulting pyrolysis gas achieved an LHV of 36.25 MJ N m³⁻. Moreover, the copyrolysis process resulted in the production of methane (CH₄) and more hydrocarbons (C₂₊), particularly ethylene (C₂H₄). The maximum yield of C₂₊ (84.86 mL·g⁻¹) was obtained when LDPE constituted 75% of the feedstock.¹⁵ FTIR analysis revealed a significant increase in CO₂ production during the copyrolysis of DS-PET. This increase in CO₂ production resulted in a reduction of the O/C ratio in the oil. The process generated organic gases like alkyls, aromatics, and carbonyls, and this effect became especially pronounced as PET initiated its decomposition. During the DS-PS copyrolysis, there was a substantial increase in alkyls, alkenes, and aromatics when the temperature exceeded 360 °C, mainly due to the degradation of PS.¹⁹ During the copyrolysis of *Nannochloropsis* sp. (NS) and *Spirulina platensis* (SP) with LDPE, there was a notable reduction in CO₂ and CO concentrations, accompanied by an increase in the proportion of C₂₊ hydrocarbons. As a result, the LHV of the pyrolysis gas improved significantly.

Overall, it can be said that the joint pyrolysis of microalgae and plastics consistently increases both the quantity and calorific value of the gas fraction, thanks to the synergistic transfer of hydrogen and more intense cracking reactions. The increase in light hydrocarbons (CH₄, C₂H₄, C₂H₆) at higher plastic content reflects the higher availability of hydrogen and carbon from polymer decomposition. At the same time, the proportional decrease in CO₂ and CO indicates more efficient deoxygenation and decarboxylation of volatile substances from algae. Among polymers, LDPE and PP generate the most energy-rich gases (up to ~36 MJ N m⁻³), while PET and PVC promote higher CO₂ formation due to their oxygen and

chlorine content. Temperature further modulates this distribution: at temperatures above 600 °C or under microwave irradiation, secondary cracking reactions dominate, increasing the C₂ + fractions and reducing residual CO₂.

These changes demonstrate that copyrolysis converts algae pyrolysis gas, which is inherently rich in CO₂, into a synthetic, hydrocarbon-rich gas suitable for energy recovery or reforming processes. Despite differences between studies, a clear general trend emerges: the addition of plastic shifts the gas phase from an oxidized to a reduced composition with high energy density, confirming the key role of hydrogen-rich polymers in improving gas product quality.

The gaseous products of copyrolysis can be utilized either as an energy carrier for combustion to produce heat, in internal combustion engines, or in combined heat and power (CHP) systems or as a feedstock for hydrogen separation and the synthesis of value-added chemicals (e.g., via Fischer–Tropsch or methanol synthesis). The copyrolysis gas mixture typically contains significant amounts of CH₄, CO, and CO₂, as well as minor fractions of H₂. For example, during catalytic cracking of plastics over biochar, the gaseous fraction has been reported to account for up to 60 wt % of the products, with hydrogen comprising approximately 60–80 vol % of the gas.³⁰ In the copyrolysis of microalgae and plastics, enhanced production of light gases, particularly hydrogen and methane, is commonly observed compared with the pyrolysis of biomass alone, as plastics act as an additional hydrogen source within the system.¹⁵ Such gas streams represent valuable energy carriers and chemical feedstocks: hydrogen can be separated for use in fuel cells or chemical synthesis, while methane and residual hydrocarbons can be combusted in conventional systems, thereby improving the overall energy efficiency of the copyrolysis process.

4.5. Summary

Operating conditions and feed composition in microalgae–plastic copyrolysis markedly affect the yields and quality of the resulting oil, gas, and char. In general, introducing hydrogen-rich plastics increases the bio-oil fraction (often exceeding 60 wt % oil at higher plastic ratios) and decreases char yield relative to microalgae alone. This is attributed to improved volatilization and hydrogen transfer from plastics, though exceptions exist; for instance, copyrolysis with PVC (a chlorine-containing plastic) can promote additional char formation via chlorine–radical reactions, showing that suboptimal feed choices or ratios may produce adverse synergies. The quality of the liquid bio-oil is substantially enhanced under copyrolysis conditions: the combined oil typically has lower oxygen and nitrogen content and a higher H/C ratio, translating into a higher heating value and greater fuel stability closer to those of conventional petroleum fuels. Experiments report that blending microalgae with plastics raises the oil's calorific value (e.g., from ~33 MJ/kg up to ~40 MJ/kg with sufficient plastic) and reduces its corrosiveness by lowering acidity and water content. Co-pyrolysis oils tend to shift toward neutral pH and contain less moisture than algae-only oils. Chemically, copyrolysis favors the generation of hydrocarbons while suppressing oxygenates; for example, increasing the plastic fraction can boost the total hydrocarbon content of the oil to nearly 100%, with minimal O- or N-compounds remaining. The solid char coproduct also undergoes beneficial changes; it becomes more carbon-rich and energy-dense when plastics are present (due to carbon

enrichment from polymer decomposition). Moreover, microalgae-derived char retains nutrient minerals (N, P, etc.), so the copyrolysis char can serve as a valuable soil amendment or catalyst support, aligning with waste-to-resource utilization. Likewise, the combustible gas yield and quality are improved: plastic addition increases the production of CH₄ and C₂₊ hydrocarbons, significantly elevating the heating value of the syngas (e.g., copyrolysis with LDPE roughly doubled the biosyngas LHV compared to microalgae-alone). In summary, by tuning feed ratios and other conditions, copyrolysis can maximize liquid fuel output with higher quality, while also generating useful char and energy-rich gas, demonstrating a clear advantage and practical value in converting algal biomass and plastic waste into sustainable energy products.

5. SYNERGISTIC EFFECTS AND MECHANISMS OF COPYROLYSIS OF MICROALGAL BIOMASS AND PLASTICS

The primary factor behind the success of the copyrolysis technique is the synergistic interactions that occur when various materials react during the process.²³ Co-pyrolysis refers to the simultaneous thermal decomposition of multiple distinct feedstocks within a shared reaction environment, characterized by the interplay between various radicals. This interaction is crucial for facilitating the production of consistent bio-oil and fosters synergistic effects vital for enhancing the qualities of biofuels.⁷¹

The distinction between theoretical and experimental outcomes of copyrolysis is the fundamental factor in analyzing the interaction between microalgae and plastics.^{27,41} The synergistic effect refers to the phenomenon where the combination of two variables has superior outcomes compared to using each variable separately. In contrast, the antagonistic effect is the direct opposite of the synergistic effect.⁴¹ The relationship between algae copyrolysis and plastics was assessed by comparing the discrepancies between the experimental and predicted outcomes,^{27,31,48,92} as summarized in eqs 1 and 2³¹ and 3–5.⁴¹

$$Y_{\text{diff}} = Y_{\text{exp.mix}} - Y_{\text{cal.mix}} \quad (1)$$

$$Y_{\text{cal.mix}} = X_{\text{microalgae}} \cdot Y_{\text{exp.microalgae}} + X_{\text{plastic}} \cdot Y_{\text{exp.plastic}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{promotion } Y_{\text{diff}} > 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{inhibition } Y_{\text{diff}} < 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{no effect } Y_{\text{diff}} = 0 \quad (5)$$

$X_{\text{microalgae}}$ and X_{plastic} are the mass percentages of microalgae and plastics in the mixtures, respectively. $Y_{\text{exp.microalgae}}$ and $Y_{\text{exp.plastic}}$ denote the experimental outcomes of microalgae and plastics pyrolysis individually, while $Y_{\text{exp.mix}}$ and $Y_{\text{cal.mix}}$ correspond to the calculated and experimental outcomes of the combined samples, respectively. A positive value for Y_{diff} demonstrates an encouraging effect of copyrolysis (the experimental value surpasses the theoretical value), whereas a negative value suggests an inhibiting impact.^{38,41}

The estimation of apparent kinetic parameters, including activation energy, pre-exponential factor, and the extent of conversion, is essential for modeling the pyrolysis behavior of biomass and related materials.⁹⁴ Pyrolysis behavior can be simulated using various modeling approaches, including multireaction mechanisms and kinetic-free models based on

Figure 3. Synergy effect of copyrolysis of microalgal biomass and plastics.

multiple heating rates. Examples of these models include the distribution activation energy model (DAEM) and methods like Popescu, Ozawa–Flynn–Wall (FWO), and Kissinger–Akahira–Sunose (KAS). The models utilize mechanistic functions that include n th-order reactions, the Amirami–Erofeev function, and independent parallel reactions (IPR).^{40,41}

Co-pyrolysis of microalgae and plastic wastes generally exhibits a synergistic reduction in the apparent activation energy compared with the pyrolysis of individual feedstocks. Molten plastics can exert a catalytic-like effect, shifting the temperature of maximum decomposition toward lower values. For example, Wu et al.⁶⁹ demonstrated that the addition of PP at a mass ratio of 6:4 reduced the apparent activation energy of microalgae from 166.9 to 144.2 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. Kong et al.⁹⁵ reported an average activation energy of approximately 180 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for a *Chlorella pyrenoidosa*–PS mixture (1:1), while Mirzaei et al.⁹⁶ reported activation energies of 122.7 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for pure microalgae, 208.2 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for pure PVC, and 180.3 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for their 1:1 mixture.

In some cases, particularly for biodegradable polymers such as PLA, a 15–30% reduction in activation energy has been observed. More broadly, comprehensive reviews on biomass-plastic copyrolysis consistently report decreases in activation energy of approximately 11–32%, underscoring the prevalence of synergistic kinetic effects.⁹⁷

The synergistic effects observed during the copyrolysis of microalgae and plastic wastes are strongly influenced by the polymer type. In general, the presence of hydrocarbon plastics with a high hydrogen content helps compensate for the hydrogen deficiency of microalgal biomass and limits the transfer of oxygen and nitrogen into the liquid products. As

shown in Figure 3, in parallel with the thermal decomposition, hydrogen transfer from polymers to biomass and reduction of oxygen and nitrogen components occur, which promotes the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons. As a result, mixed-feedstock pyrolysis produces higher-quality bio-oil with a lower heteroatom content compared with the pyrolysis of microalgae alone. However, the resulting synergistic effects are case-specific, as some polymer microalgae combinations promote higher liquid yields, whereas others preferentially enhance gas formation or solid char production. The following sections provide an overview of the dominant synergistic mechanisms associated with the main classes of plastics (PE, PP, PS, PVC, and PET)^{3,27,28} supplemented by biodegradable polymers.^{15,99}

5.1. Polyethylene (PE)

Polyethylene, particularly in the form of low-density (LDPE) or high-density polyethylene (HDPE), generates abundant volatile hydrogen-rich radicals during pyrolysis, which can readily interact with fragments derived from microalgal biomass. This interaction promotes chain scission and hydrogenation of oxygenated compounds, thereby enhancing the formation of lighter hydrocarbon products. As a result of these synergistic interactions, the oxygen content of the bio-oil is reduced, with a larger fraction of oxygen being removed in the form of H_2O , CO , or CO_2 . For example, Tang et al.¹⁵ reported that during the copyrolysis of *Nannochloropsis* microalgae with LDPE, the optimal biomass-to-plastic ratio for maximizing liquid yield was approximately 3:1, whereas higher plastic contents led to excessive gas formation. Other studies have shown that increasing the PE fraction in the feedstock reduces coke (solid residue) yield due to the high volatility of PE and promotes secondary cracking of heavier oil fractions into gaseous products. In contrast, the effect of PE on

bio-oil yield can be ambiguous. At moderate PE loadings, both the quantity and quality of bio-oil are improved; however, excessively high PE contents may decrease liquid yield, as a substantial fraction of carbon is converted into gaseous products.⁸⁵ Recent studies further indicate that the molecular structure of PE also influences product distribution. For instance, Hou et al.⁹⁸ found that linear PE chains effectively reduce nitrogen-containing compounds in microalgal bio-oil but simultaneously increase the oxygen content, whereas branched PE mitigates this oxygen increase.

5.2. Polypropylene (PP)

The copyrolysis of microalgae with polypropylene exhibits hydrogenation-driven synergistic effects similar to those observed with PE, as PP is likewise rich in hydrogen and carbon. The addition of PP significantly reduces the energetic barrier of biomass decomposition; both experimental and computational studies have reported a lower overall activation energy for copyrolysis compared with the pyrolysis of microalgae alone. Thermogravimetric analyses have further shown that increasing the PP fraction in the feedstock decreases the temperature corresponding to the maximum decomposition rate of microalgae, indicating an acceleration of biomass degradation induced by the plastic. The synergistic effect is also reflected in the suppression of solid residue formation. Polypropylene itself produces negligible coke, and the radicals released during its decomposition facilitate the disruption of microalgal char structures.¹⁹ Consequently, higher yields of gaseous and liquid products are obtained at the expense of the solid fraction.

In parallel, the composition of the bio-oil is markedly improved. Co-pyrolysis of *Chlorella vulgaris* with PP has been shown to suppress the formation of aromatic and nitrogen-containing heterocycles associated with Maillard-type reactions, while promoting the generation of aliphatic hydrocarbons in the oil phase. Jiang et al.⁹² reported that at an optimal PP mass fraction of approximately 3:1 (75 wt % PP and 25 wt % biomass), the highest hydrocarbon yield in bio-oil was achieved, accompanied by a maximum reduction in the activation energy of decomposition.

5.3. Polystyrene (PS)

The copyrolysis of microalgae with polystyrene behaves distinctly from that with polyolefins. PS generates predominantly aromatic radicals (e.g., styrenic fragments), which exhibit lower reactivity toward oxygenated biomass-derived intermediates. As a result, polystyrene does not promote oxygen removal to the gas phase as effectively as PE or PP.

Several studies have shown that the addition of PS can actually increase the yield of liquid products. For example, Suriapparao et al.⁸⁵ reported during microwave-assisted pyrolysis that a mixture of fresh *Chlorella* biomass and expanded polystyrene (EPS) produced up to 65 wt % bio-oil, which was substantially higher than that obtained from the same algal feedstock copyrolyzed with PE (~40 wt %) or PP (~45 wt %) under identical conditions. This behavior has been attributed to the lower tendency of volatile oxygenated compounds from algal biomass to react with aromatic PS-derived fragments, forming CO₂ and H₂O, compared to their reactions with saturated hydrocarbons derived from PE or PP. Consequently, a smaller fraction of biomass-derived oxygen is transferred to the gas phase, and a larger fraction remains in the liquid products, resulting in increased oil yield, albeit with a higher oxygen content.

Similar conclusions were drawn by Chen et al.¹⁹ in their review, which reported that PS exhibits a product distribution distinct from that of paraffinic plastics. An additional beneficial effect is the reduction in solid residue formation. The copyrolysis of *Dunaliella salina* with PS has been shown to decrease char yield relative to expected values, owing to hydrogenation reactions between unsaturated biomass-derived intermediates and the decomposing polymer. Overall, aromatic species derived from PS contribute to the enhanced decomposition of algal biomass, promoting the formation of energy-dense liquid fuels.

5.4. Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC)

Polyvinyl chloride is considered one of the more problematic plastics due to the release of HCl and chlorinated compounds during thermal degradation. However, when copyrolyzed with microalgae, notable synergistic interactions can occur. Even small additions of PVC have been shown to influence the mechanisms of biomass decomposition. For example, Dai et al.⁷¹ observed during microwave-assisted pyrolysis of *Chlorella vulgaris* with PVC that certain blend compositions led to an increase in char yield (approximately 1.36 wt % at 50 wt % PVC), attributed to physicochemical interactions between the two components.¹⁹ Mirzaei et al.,⁹⁶ for example, found that the addition of *Chlorella vulgaris* microalgae shifts the maximum HCl release temperature from 309 °C (PVC alone) to ~274 °C, thus accelerating/inducing dechlorination at a lower temperature due to synergistic interactions.

At higher PVC proportions, however, this trend reverses. Further increases in PVC content led to a decrease in solid residue formation and a pronounced increase in gas yield, at the expense of liquid products, with the gaseous fraction rising from ~20% to ~58% as the algae-to-PVC ratio shifted from 7:3 to 3:7.⁷¹ This behavior is consistent with the degradation characteristics of PVC, which predominantly produces gaseous and liquid species and comparatively little solid carbon. Importantly, synergistic effects are favorably reflected in the quality of bio-oil. Chlorine introduced by PVC is largely retained in the solid residue and ash, thereby reducing the chlorine content of the oil phase.^{16,32} Microalgae inherently contain mineral constituents (ash rich in Ca and Mg, for example), which can act as HCl sorbents, mitigating product corrosivity. Lv et al.¹² reported that during the copyrolysis of protein-rich microalgae with PVC, an increasing PVC content significantly reduced the concentration of nitrogen- and oxygen-containing organic compounds in the bio-oil.

In parallel, a substantial improvement in the higher heating value (HHV) of the resulting oil has been reported. According to Dai et al., the HHV increased from 33.05 MJ kg⁻¹ for pure microalgal biomass to 39.73 MJ kg⁻¹ at higher PVC loadings, due to synergistic hydrogenation and deoxygenation pathways.⁷¹ Thermogravimetric analyses further indicate that the presence of PVC alters the thermal decomposition profile of microalgae, introducing distinct degradation stages and overall reducing the activation energy required for thermal conversion.³⁸ These findings demonstrate that, when appropriately combined, microalgal biomass and PVC can simultaneously mitigate halogen-related emissions while enhancing the fuel properties of microalgae-derived bio-oil.

5.5. Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET)

PET is a polyester containing a substantial amount of oxygen in its molecular structure, which strongly influences its behavior during copyrolysis. The addition of PET to microalgal

biomass promotes more intensive deoxygenation reactions, resulting in increased evolution of CO₂, CO, and H₂O and consequently reducing the relative oxygen content of the liquid products. Chen et al.¹⁹ reported that during the pyrolysis of *Dunaliella salina* mixed with PET, CO₂ production increased markedly compared with that from the individual feedstocks, leading to a lower O/C ratio in the resulting bio-oil. Similarly, Tang et al.¹⁵ observed enhanced CO₂ evolution during the copyrolysis of microalgae with PET, as determined by FTIR analysis, which resulted in a less oxygenated oil phase.

This synergistic effect, namely, the preferential partitioning of oxygen into the gas phase, is highly desirable, as it improves bio-oil quality by reducing the content of oxygenated species (e.g., acids and ketones), thereby enhancing oil stability and heating value. At the same time, the overall liquid yield may decrease slightly, since a portion of PET-derived carbon is converted into gaseous products (CO₂ and light hydrocarbons) rather than condensable oils. Conversely, the resulting bio-oil tends to contain a higher proportion of aromatic compounds originating from PET decomposition (e.g., benzene, toluene, and styrene from phenyl group scission), which can further increase the energy density of the fuel. Overall, PET can be regarded as a synergistic coprocessing component with respect to oxygen removal, as its presence facilitates the release of biomass-derived oxygen in the form of CO₂ and H₂O, leaving the bio-oil enriched in hydrocarbon species. These molecular interactions and reaction pathways during the copyrolysis of microalgae with PET and other plastics are discussed in detail in the recent review by Chen and Yang,³⁴ which summarizes current knowledge on synergistic products and reaction mechanisms. Recent studies, therefore, confirm that appropriately combining microalgae with polymeric plastics, including PET, results in pronounced synergistic effects manifested by improved bio-oil quality and enhanced energy recovery.

5.6. Biodegradable Plastics

Biodegradable polymers such as polylactic acid (PLA), polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs, e.g., polyhydroxybutyrate), poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT), and poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) have recently been investigated in copyrolysis with microalgae. These bioplastics generally undergo thermal degradation at lower temperatures (approximately 250–380 °C) than conventional fossil-based plastics; for example, PLA and PHB typically decompose at around 273–378 °C, whereas polyolefins such as PE, PP, or polystyrene degrade at higher temperatures, usually in the range of ~386–499 °C.¹⁰⁰

During the copyrolysis of microalgae with conventional plastics, pronounced synergistic effects are commonly observed. Hydrogen released from polyolefins facilitates the in situ hydrogenation of biomass-derived intermediates, thereby reducing the oxygen and nitrogen contents in the resulting bio-oil. For instance, Tang et al.¹⁵ reported that the addition of 25 wt % polyethylene during the pyrolysis of *Nannochloropsis* increased the proportion of aliphatic hydrocarbons in the bio-oil from 22.6% to 77.4%, while drastically suppressing oxygen- and nitrogen-containing compounds. In this case, oxygen was preferentially released as H₂O and CO (rather than CO₂, as in the pyrolysis of pure biomass), and nitrogen was transferred to the gas phase, leading to a substantial improvement in liquid product quality. Overall, copyrolysis with polyolefins inhibits the incorporation of O

and N into bio-oil and promotes their removal in the form of H₂O, CO₂, or gaseous nitrogen species.²⁹

In contrast, the behavior of biodegradable plastics differs markedly. These polymers intrinsically contain high levels of heteroatoms, particularly oxygen; therefore, the copyrolysis of microalgae with PLA, PHA, or related materials does not yield bio-oils as hydrocarbon-rich as those obtained with polyolefins. Instead, product distributions are typically enriched in oxygenated compounds (e.g., alcohols, esters, and organic acids), accompanied by increased formation of noncondensable gases (CO and CO₂). Nevertheless, Xu et al.⁹⁹ observed certain synergistic effects during the copyrolysis of microalgae with PLA, where molten PLA partially encapsulated biomass particles, thereby slowing the release of volatiles and reducing the activation energy of decomposition by approximately 15–30% compared to the pyrolysis of microalgae alone. At the same time, higher microalgae contents promoted increased formation of H₂O and CO₂ (reflecting dehydration and decarboxylation reactions), whereas higher PLA fractions enhanced the formation of carbonyl-containing compounds and slightly suppressed CH₄ production. Adachi et al.¹⁰⁰ further demonstrated that under slow heating conditions, biodegradable polyesters and conventional plastics tend to decompose largely independently, within distinct temperature ranges, with limited mutual interaction. As a consequence, bio-oils derived from copyrolysis with PLA, PHA, or similar biopolymers generally exhibit higher oxygen contents and lower heating values than those produced in combination with polyolefins.¹⁰¹ This often results in lower yields of high-quality liquid fuel fractions and reduced oil stability, necessitating additional upgrading or refining.

On the other hand, biodegradable polymers do not contain halogens (unlike PVC) or other hazardous additives, thereby reducing the risk of toxic emissions during thermochemical processing. From a life-cycle perspective, bioplastics also offer environmental advantages: they are derived from renewable resources and, during degradation or pyrolysis, partially return biogenic carbon to the cycle, aligning with broader strategies aimed at reducing the carbon footprint of advanced materials.¹⁰⁰

5.7. Summary

In summary, the chemical nature of plastics fundamentally determines the type and magnitude of synergistic effects during copyrolysis with microalgal biomass. Polyolefins (PE and PP) act as hydrogen donors, stabilizing biomass-derived radicals and thereby suppressing char formation, while increasing the yields of gaseous products and high-quality oil fractions. Aromatic polystyrene (PS) tends to enhance liquid yields, albeit without a pronounced reduction in oxygenated compounds, whereas halogenated PVC requires effective chlorine capture but can substantially improve the energy content of bio-oil while simultaneously suppressing nitrogen- and oxygen-containing impurities. Oxygen-rich PET facilitates oxygen removal from the overall system in the form of gaseous species, resulting in a significantly deoxygenated and more hydrogenated bio-oil composition.

Biodegradable polyesters (e.g., PLA) exhibit distinct behavior during copyrolysis, characterized by facile degradation into volatile products (typically lactide rather than low-molecular-weight oxygenates), which promotes reaction progress and limits solid residue formation, even though these polymers do not contribute additional hydrogen to the

system as polyolefins do. A detailed understanding of these molecular-level mechanisms is essential for the rational optimization of copyrolysis processes. As demonstrated by recent studies (e.g., Razzak et al.,³³), the appropriate selection of plastic type and blending ratio enables targeted control over reaction pathways and product yields, allowing maximization of desirable fuel fractions while minimizing undesirable byproducts.

Ongoing research conducted between 2022 and 2025 has provided deeper insights into radical-driven synergistic interactions, thereby paving the way for efficient coprocessing of microalgal biomass and plastic wastes toward sustainable energy recovery.

6. CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

Insufficient understanding of kinetics and synergistic mechanisms: although existing studies demonstrate that the copyrolysis of microalgae and plastics can produce pronounced synergistic effects such as reduced activation energy requirements and increased yields of desirable products, the underlying mechanisms remain insufficiently understood.^{19,92} In particular, the roles of free-radical reactions, as well as interactions between gaseous and solid-phase intermediates, have not yet been comprehensively elucidated, which complicates rational and systematic kinetic investigations and in-depth mechanistic analyses of copyrolysis reactions.

Advanced modeling approaches: the quantitative prediction and understanding of complex copyrolysis processes require the application of multiphase and multistep models. For instance, multistep distributed activation energy models (multi-DAEM) can distinguish different “pseudo-components” and more accurately describe the thermal decomposition behavior of complex feedstock mixtures.¹⁰² In addition, the integration of phase-interaction models and machine learning techniques appears particularly promising. Recent studies have demonstrated that predictive models such as those based on XGBoost can estimate bio-oil yields from feedstock composition with high accuracy.¹⁰³ Such approaches would enable the prediction of the behavior of realistic microalgae-plastic mixtures and the optimization of operating conditions prior to experimental validation.

Experimental methodologies under realistic conditions: laboratory studies commonly employ pure microalgal cultures and model plastics, although industrial or environmental biomass may contain various contaminants (e.g., salts, heavy metals, and biological impurities). Waste plastics, on the other hand, typically consist of mixed polymer types with diverse additives, such as pigments and stabilizers. For example, Chen et al.¹⁹ demonstrated that chlorine released from PVC can react with microalgae-derived pyrolysis products (e.g., alkyl species reacting with HCl), thereby altering both the yield and composition of the solid residue. Future research should therefore aim to better simulate real-world conditions, for instance by investigating mixed plastic streams (PP, PE, PS, PET, PVC, etc.) and the presence of common contaminants, in order to obtain more realistic data on product yields and product quality.

Pilot and demonstration scale studies: most existing investigations have been conducted at the laboratory scale (e.g., thermogravimetric analysis and benchtop reactors), while data from pilot-scale facilities or continuous demonstration units remain scarce. Without such data, it is difficult to reliably assess the transferability of laboratory-derived findings to

practical applications, including realistic product yields, operational stability, and heat-transfer limitations, as well as to evaluate techno-economic feasibility under real operating conditions. This gap is further emphasized by the fact that many existing life cycle assessment (LCA) studies have been based primarily on laboratory or early pilot data with incomplete process information, thereby limiting the robustness of sustainability evaluations.

Reactor configurations: the development of reactor systems specifically optimized for the copyrolysis of mixed feedstocks is crucial. Conventional pyrolysis reactors (e.g., fluidized beds, vacuum furnaces, and tubular reactors) require adaptation to accommodate the combined processing of biomass and plastics. More advanced approaches include the use of microwave-assisted pyrolyzers and catalytic reactors with integrated sorption functionalities. Recent studies have shown that the incorporation of microwave absorbers (e.g., SiC) and metal-based catalysts (e.g., MgO) can significantly enhance energy efficiency and conversion performance: SiC accelerates heating rates and has been reported to increase bio-oil yield by approximately 4%, while MgO lowers decomposition energy barriers and enhances gas production by about 12%.¹⁰⁴ Further research should explore innovative reactor configurations, such as the combined injection of biomass and catalysts, zoned reactor designs, and rotary kilns, to improve heat-transfer efficiency and achieve more effective phase separation during copyrolysis.

Integration with complementary processes: integrating copyrolysis with additional process steps represents a promising research direction. Catalysts can be incorporated directly into the pyrolysis stage, such as zeolites, metal oxides, or biochar, to tailor product composition. For example, ZSM-5 and activated carbon promote the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons and hydrogen, whereas alkaline catalysts reduce the content of organic acids and nitrogen-containing compounds.¹⁰⁴ Postpyrolysis hydroprocessing steps, including catalytic hydrogenation of pyrolysis oils, can further remove heteroatoms and produce more stable fuel fractions. While integration with hydroprocessing or other upgrading technologies has the potential to significantly enhance the quality of resulting biofuels and chemicals, it also requires dedicated research efforts, particularly in terms of catalyst selection, temperature regimes, and hydrogen management strategies.

Energy and environmental assessment: to verify the overall benefits of copyrolysis, comprehensive evaluations of energy consumption and environmental impacts are required. Existing life cycle assessment (LCA) studies indicate that biomass preparation steps such as fertilization, drying, and transportation constitute a significant share of total environmental impacts. In particular, drying of microalgal biomass prior to pyrolysis is highly energy-intensive. However, fully integrated LCA studies covering the entire copyrolysis value chain from microalgae cultivation and plastic waste management to final product utilization are still lacking. Moreover, comparative assessments against alternative waste management and energy recovery pathways (e.g., direct plastic incineration or biological waste treatment) remain scarce.¹⁰⁵ Such analyses should also address greenhouse gas emissions, wastewater quality, and the potential utilization of biochar. Without these comprehensive assessments, the true sustainability of proposed copyrolysis technologies cannot be reliably determined.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The conducted review indicates that copyrolysis of microalgae and plastics is a promising pathway for producing alternative fuels and chemicals from waste-derived feedstocks. The combined processing of these materials overcomes the kinetic limitations of biomass-only pyrolysis by reducing the activation energy required for thermal decomposition. Furthermore, this method improves product quality by increasing the fraction of aliphatic hydrocarbons and reducing the formation of aromatic and nitrogen-containing compounds. The addition of polyolefin plastics to the pyrolysis of microalgae improves the quality of the produced bio-oil by lowering its oxygen content and the proportion of unsaturated compounds, thereby enhancing oxidative stability and extending storage lifetime. At the same time, such bio-oil more closely resembles conventional fossil fuels in terms of its properties, including higher energy density and greater nonpolarity.

Despite these positive findings, significant research gaps remain. A reliable assessment of the benefits and sustainability of copyrolysis processes requires comprehensive life-cycle analyses (LCAs) that encompass both environmental and energy balances across the entire value chain, from feedstock preparation to final products. Many published studies rely primarily on laboratory-scale or limited pilot-scale data and do not adequately account for energy demands at larger scales (e.g., biomass drying or product separation), thereby limiting the robustness of existing evaluations. Moreover, the overall economic feasibility of microalgae-plastic copyrolysis has not yet been systematically assessed, representing a key direction for future research. For practical implementation, further studies should focus on several specific areas: validation of the process at larger (pilot-scale) conditions; the development of complete LCA and techno-economic analyses to assess real sustainability and cost-effectiveness; and the design of optimized reactor configurations, including the integration of downstream catalytic upgrading steps, to enhance process efficiency and product quality. Overall, although the copyrolysis of microalgae and plastics offers considerable environmental and technical advantages, its practical deployment will ultimately depend on thorough validation at industrially relevant scales and on comprehensive assessments of both sustainability and economic performance.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

Wei-Hsin Chen – *Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, National Cheng Kung University, Tainan 701, Taiwan; Research Center for Smart Sustainable Circular Economy, Tunghai University, Taichung 407, Taiwan; Department of Mechanical Engineering, National Chin-Yi University of Technology, Taichung 411, Taiwan;* orcid.org/0000-0001-5009-3960; Email: weihsinchen@gmail.com, chenwh@mail.ncku.edu.tw

Authors

Michal Safar – *Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, National Cheng Kung University, Tainan 701, Taiwan; CEET/ENET Centre, VŠB-Technical University of Ostrava, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic;* orcid.org/0000-0002-6634-7432

Dagmar Juchelkova – *Department of Electronics, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, VSB—*

Technical University of Ostrava, Ostrava-Poruba 708 00, Czech Republic

Helena Raclavska – *CEET/ENET Centre, VŠB-Technical University of Ostrava, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic*

Barbora Svedova – *CEET/ENET Centre, VŠB-Technical University of Ostrava, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic*

Jamin Jamir Escalante – *Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics and International Doctoral Degree Program on Energy Engineering, National Cheng Kung University, Tainan 701, Taiwan*

Complete contact information is available at:

<https://pubs.acs.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.5c06034>

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

Biographies

He received his Ph.D. in Energy Engineering and a second doctoral degree in Waste Processing from VSB—Technical University of Ostrava, where he currently serves as a senior researcher at the CEET research center. His research focuses on the thermochemical conversion of biomass and plastics, particularly pyrolysis and copyrolysis for biofuel production. He has published several peer-reviewed studies on energy recovery from waste biomass and plastic materials.

He received his Ph.D. degree from National Cheng Kung University and is a distinguished professor in the Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics (DAA) and the Director of the Energy Industry Talent Education Center (EITEC) at the same institution. He is also a Chair Professor at Tunghai University and National Chin-Yi University of Technology and a Research Fellow of the National Science and Technology Council, Taiwan. He is recognized as one of the leading international experts in bioenergy and biofuel.

She holds a Ph.D. in Energy Engineering from VSB-TUO, where she is currently a professor. Her research focuses on the utilization of biomass and waste for energy, including combustion, pyrolysis, and the mitigation of environmental impacts. She has served as Head of the Department of Energy Engineering and contributed to the efficient use of byproducts in energy systems. Her work emphasizes sustainable energy technologies and reducing emissions from the conversion of alternative fuels.

She is a Professor and Head of Laboratory at VSB-TUO. She earned her CSc. degree in Chemistry and Fuel Technology. Her research focuses on residues from combustion and pyrolysis, especially ashes and biochar, and their practical applications. She specializes in waste characterization, fuel chemistry, and the material use of thermally treated waste products, supporting circular economy principles.

She is a researcher at VSB—Technical University of Ostrava. She has Ph.D. degrees in environmental and energy engineering. She is a researcher at the Centre ENET/CEET. Her research addresses biodegradable waste, biochar in the circular economy, air pollution (PM, VOCs, Heavy metals), emission source identification, and alternative energy sources (plastic waste recovery). She studies pyrolysis, biochar, and clean energy. She also studies air pollution and its environmental risks.

He obtained his Master's degree in Energy Engineering from National Cheng Kung University and is currently pursuing a Ph.D. in the same field at NCKU, Taiwan. His research focuses on advanced waste-to-

energy technologies, with an emphasis on catalytic copyrolysis, gasification, and steam reforming of waste biomass, as well as developing methods to enhance syngas quality. His current work integrates thermochemical conversion, biochar-based catalysts, and data-driven optimization to advance circular bioeconomy strategies.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This article is supported by the ESF in “Waste as an alternative source of energy” project, reg. nr. CZ.02.01.01/00/23_021/0008590 within the Programme Johannes Amos Comenius. The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support from the National Science and Technology Council, Taiwan, R.O.C, under the contracts NSTC 114-2218-E-006-013- and NSTC 114-2218-E-002-020-for this study. This research was also supported in part by Higher Education Sprout Project, Ministry of Education to the Headquarters of University Advancement at National Cheng Kung University (NCKU).

REFERENCES

- (1) Debnath, C.; Bandyopadhyay, T. K.; Bhunia, B.; Mishra, U.; Narayanasamy, S.; Muthuraj, M. Microalgae: Sustainable resource of carbohydrates in third-generation biofuel production. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2021**, *150*, 111464.
- (2) Chen, W.-H.; Lin, B.-J.; Huang, M.-Y.; Chang, J.-S. Thermochemical conversion of microalgal biomass into biofuels: A review. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2015**, *184*, 314–327.
- (3) Mat Aron, N. S.; Khoo, K. S.; Chew, K. W.; Show, P. L.; Chen, W.; Nguyen, T. H. P. Sustainability of the four generations of biofuels - A review. *Int. J. Energy Res.* **2020**, *44*, 9266–9282.
- (4) Lü, J.; Sheahan, C.; Fu, P. Metabolic engineering of algae for fourth generation biofuels production. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2011**, *4*, 2451.
- (5) Li, S.; Li, F.; Zhu, X.; Liao, Q.; Chang, J.-S.; Ho, S.-H. Biohydrogen production from microalgae for environmental sustainability. *Chemosphere* **2022**, *291*, 132717.
- (6) Khan, M. I.; Shin, J. H.; Kim, J. D. The promising future of microalgae: current status, challenges, and optimization of a sustainable and renewable industry for biofuels, feed, and other products. *Microb. Cell Fact.* **2018**, *17*, 36.
- (7) Ho, S.-H.; Huang, S.-W.; Chen, C.-Y.; Hasunuma, T.; Kondo, A.; Chang, J.-S. Bioethanol production using carbohydrate-rich microalgal biomass as feedstock. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2013**, *135*, 191–198.
- (8) Ganesh Saratale, R.; Kumar, G.; Banu, R.; Xia, A.; Periyasamy, S.; Dattatraya Saratale, G. A critical review on anaerobic digestion of microalgae and macroalgae and co-digestion of biomass for enhanced methane generation. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2018**, *262*, 319–332.
- (9) Goh, B. H. H.; Ong, H. C.; Cheah, M. Y.; Chen, W.-H.; Yu, K. L.; Mahlia, T. M. I. Sustainability of direct biodiesel synthesis from microalgal biomass: A critical review. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2019**, *107*, 59–74.
- (10) López Barreiro, D.; Prins, W.; Ronsse, F.; Brilman, W. Hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) of microalgae for biofuel production: State of the art review and future prospects. *Biomass Bioenergy* **2013**, *53*, 113–127.
- (11) Magalhães, I. B.; Pereira, A. S. A. D. P.; Silva, T. A.; Renato, N. D. S. Predicting the higher heating value of microalgae biomass based on proximate and ultimate analysis. *Algal Res.* **2022**, *64*, 102677.
- (12) Lv, X.; Liu, H.; Huang, Y.; Yao, J.; Yuan, H.; Yin, X.; et al. Synergistic effects on co-pyrolysis of low-temperature hydrothermally pretreated high-protein microalgae and polypropylene. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2021**, *229*, 113772.
- (13) Dai, L.; Zhou, N.; Lv, Y.; Cheng, Y.; Wang, Y.; Liu, Y.; et al. Pyrolysis technology for plastic waste recycling: A state-of-the-art review. *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* **2022**, *93*, 101021.
- (14) Burra, K. G.; Gupta, A. K. Synergistic effects in steam gasification of combined biomass and plastic waste mixtures. *Appl. Energy* **2018**, *211*, 230–236.
- (15) Tang, Z.; Chen, W.; Chen, Y.; Yang, H.; Chen, H. Co-pyrolysis of microalgae and plastic: Characteristics and interaction effects. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2019**, *274*, 145–152.
- (16) Ahmed, M. H. M.; Batalha, N.; Mahmudul, H. M. D.; Perkins, G.; Konarova, M. A review on advanced catalytic co-pyrolysis of biomass and hydrogen-rich feedstock: Insights into synergistic effect, catalyst development and reaction mechanism. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2020**, *310*, 123457.
- (17) Praveen Kumar, K.; Srinivas, S. Catalytic Co-pyrolysis of Biomass and Plastics (Polypropylene and Polystyrene) Using Spent FCC Catalyst. *Energy Fuels* **2020**, *34*, 460–473.
- (18) Wang, Z.; Burra, K. G.; Lei, T.; Gupta, A. K. Co-pyrolysis of waste plastic and solid biomass for synergistic production of biofuels and chemicals-A review. *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* **2021**, *84*, 100899.
- (19) Chen, R.; Zhang, S.; Yang, X.; Li, G.; Zhou, H.; Li, Q.; et al. Thermal behaviour and kinetic study of co-pyrolysis of microalgae with different plastics. *Waste Manag.* **2021**, *126*, 331–339.
- (20) Vuppaladadiyam, A. K.; Vuppaladadiyam, S. S. V.; Awasthi, A.; Sahoo, A.; Rehman, S.; Pant, K. K.; et al. Biomass pyrolysis: A review on recent advancements and green hydrogen production. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2022**, *364*, 128087.
- (21) Huang, Y.; Qiu, S.; Oduro, I. N.; Guo, X.; Fang, Y. Production of High-Yield Bio-oil with a High Effective Hydrogen/Carbon Molar Ratio through Acidolysis and In Situ Hydrogenation. *Energy Fuels* **2016**, *30*, 9524–9531.
- (22) Uzoejinwa, B. B.; He, X.; Wang, S.; El-Fatah Abomohra, A.; Hu, Y.; Wang, Q. Co-pyrolysis of biomass and waste plastics as a thermochemical conversion technology for high-grade biofuel production: Recent progress and future directions elsewhere worldwide. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2018**, *163*, 468–492.
- (23) Abnisa, F.; Wan Daud, W. M. A. A review on co-pyrolysis of biomass: An optional technique to obtain a high-grade pyrolysis oil. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2014**, *87*, 71–85.
- (24) Ryu, H. W.; Kim, D. H.; Jae, J.; Lam, S. S.; Park, E. D.; Park, Y.-K. Recent advances in catalytic co-pyrolysis of biomass and plastic waste for the production of petroleum-like hydrocarbons. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2020**, *310*, 123473.
- (25) Azizi, K.; Keshavarz Moraveji, M.; Abedini Najafabadi, H. A review on bio-fuel production from microalgal biomass by using pyrolysis method. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2018**, *82*, 3046–3059.
- (26) Lee, J.; Kwon, E. E.; Park, Y.-K. Recent advances in the catalytic pyrolysis of microalgae. *Catal. Today* **2020**, *355*, 263–271.
- (27) Su, G.; Ong, H. C.; Gan, Y. Y.; Chen, W.-H.; Chong, C. T.; Ok, Y. S. Co-pyrolysis of microalgae and other biomass wastes for the production of high-quality bio-oil: Progress and prospective. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2022**, *344*, 126096.
- (28) Ebadi, S.; Lee, J.; Nam, H.; Jung, S.; Seo, M. W.; Lee, D.; et al. Recent advances in copyrolysis of algal biomass with waste plastics for the production of upgraded oil. *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* **2026**, *194*, 107538.
- (29) Nawaz, A.; Haddad, H.; Shah, M. A.; Uddin, S.; Hossain, M. M.; Abdur Razzak, S. Fueling sustainability: Co-pyrolysis of microalgae biomass and waste plastics for renewable energy and waste mitigation. *Biomass Bioenergy* **2024**, *187*, 107303.
- (30) Khder, I. M.; Abdulkareem, H. A.; Hassan, Z. F.; Gheni, S. A.; Hamd, M. I.; Ahmed, N. N.; et al. Advances in catalytic pyrolysis of mixed plastic waste with algal biomass: A review on sustainable biofuel production and carbon capture. *Clean Waste Syst.* **2025**, *12*, 100434.
- (31) Tang, Z.; Chen, W.; Hu, J.; Li, S.; Chen, Y.; Yang, H.; et al. Co-pyrolysis of microalgae with low-density polyethylene (LDPE) for deoxygenation and denitrification. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2020**, *311*, 123502.
- (32) Lachos-Perez, D.; Martins-Vieira, J. C.; Missau, J.; Anshu, K.; Siakpebru, O. K.; Thengane, S. K.; et al. Review on Biomass Pyrolysis with a Focus on Bio-Oil Upgrading Techniques. *Analytica* **2023**, *4*, 182–205.
- (33) Razzak, S. A.; Haddad, H.; Nawaz, A.; Hossain, M. M. Review for the synergistic effects in catalytic co-pyrolysis of biomass and

- plastic waste: Pathways to sustainable energy. *Next Sustain.* **2025**, *6*, 100157.
- (34) Chen, B.; Yang, Y. Co-pyrolysis of algae with other carbon-based materials: a review on synergistic products and molecular reaction pathway. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* **2023**, *148*, 2233–2249.
- (35) Lee, X. J.; Ong, H. C.; Gan, Y. Y.; Chen, W.-H.; Mahlia, T. M. I. State of art review on conventional and advanced pyrolysis of macroalgae and microalgae for biochar, bio-oil and bio-syngas production. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2020**, *210*, 112707.
- (36) Escalante, J.; Chen, W.-H.; Tabatabaei, M.; Hoang, A. T.; Kwon, E. E.; Andrew Lin, K.-Y.; et al. Pyrolysis of lignocellulosic, algal, plastic, and other biomass wastes for biofuel production and circular bioeconomy: A review of thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) approach. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2022**, *169*, 112914.
- (37) Al-Rumaihi, A.; Shahbaz, M.; McKay, G.; Mackey, H.; Al-Ansari, T. A review of pyrolysis technologies and feedstock: A blending approach for plastic and biomass towards optimum biochar yield. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2022**, *167*, 112715.
- (38) Rasam, S.; Azizi, K.; Moraveji, M. K.; Akbari, A.; Soria-Verdugo, A. Insights into the co-pyrolysis of olive stone, waste polyvinyl chloride and Spirulina microalgae blends through thermogravimetric analysis. *Algal Res.* **2022**, *62*, 102635.
- (39) Potnuri, R.; Suriapparao, D. V.; Rao, C. S.; Kumar, T. H. Understanding the role of modeling and simulation in pyrolysis of biomass and waste plastics: A review. *Bioresour. Technol. Rep.* **2022**, *20*, 101221.
- (40) Yang, C.; Li, R.; Zhang, B.; Qiu, Q.; Wang, B.; Yang, H.; et al. Pyrolysis of microalgae: A critical review. *Fuel Process. Technol.* **2019**, *186*, 53–72.
- (41) Aniza, R.; Chen, W.-H.; Lin, Y.-Y.; Tran, K.-Q.; Chang, J.-S.; Lam, S. S.; et al. Independent parallel pyrolysis kinetics of extracted proteins and lipids as well as model carbohydrates in microalgae. *Appl. Energy* **2021**, *300*, 117372.
- (42) Guedes, R. E.; Luna, A. S.; Torres, A. R. Operating parameters for bio-oil production in biomass pyrolysis: A review. *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* **2018**, *129*, 134–149.
- (43) Chang, Y.-M.; Tsai, W.-T.; Li, M.-H. Chemical characterization of char derived from slow pyrolysis of microalgal residue. *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* **2015**, *111*, 88–93.
- (44) Anand, V.; Sunjeev, V.; Vinu, R. Catalytic fast pyrolysis of *Arthrospira platensis* (spirulina) algae using zeolites. *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* **2016**, *118*, 298–307.
- (45) Tan, H.; Lee, C. T.; Ong, P. Y.; Wong, K. Y.; Bong, C. P. C.; Li, C.; et al. A Review On The Comparison Between Slow Pyrolysis And Fast Pyrolysis On The Quality Of Lignocellulosic And Lignin-Based Biochar. *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.* **2021**, *1051*, 012075.
- (46) Tripathi, M.; Sahu, J. N.; Ganesan, P. Effect of process parameters on production of biochar from biomass waste through pyrolysis: A review. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2016**, *55*, 467–481.
- (47) Pattiya, A. Catalytic pyrolysis. In *Direct Thermochem. Liq. Energy Appl.*; Elsevier, 2018; pp 29–64.
- (48) Qi, P.; Chang, G.; Wang, H.; Zhang, X.; Guo, Q. Production of aromatic hydrocarbons by catalytic co-pyrolysis of microalgae and polypropylene using HZSM-5. *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* **2018**, *136*, 178–185.
- (49) Borges, F. C.; Xie, Q.; Min, M.; Muniz, L. A. R.; Farenzena, M.; Trierweiler, J. O.; et al. Fast microwave-assisted pyrolysis of microalgae using microwave absorbent and HZSM-5 catalyst. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2014**, *166*, 518–526.
- (50) Mutsengerere, S.; Chihobo, C. H.; Musademba, D.; Nhapi, I. A review of operating parameters affecting bio-oil yield in microwave pyrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2019**, *104*, 328–336.
- (51) Yan, W.-H.; Wang, K.; Duan, P.-G.; Wang, B.; Wang, F.; Shi, X.-L.; et al. Catalytic hydrolysis and co-hydrolysis of algae and used engine oil for the production of hydrocarbon-rich fuel. *Energy* **2017**, *133*, 1153–1162.
- (52) Suali, E.; Sarbatly, R. Conversion of microalgae to biofuel. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2012**, *16*, 4316–4342.
- (53) Babich, I. V.; Van Der Hulst, M.; Lefferts, L.; Moulijn, J. A.; O'Connor, P.; Seshan, K. Catalytic pyrolysis of microalgae to high-quality liquid bio-fuels. *Biomass Bioenergy* **2011**, *35*, 3199–3207.
- (54) Fakayode, O. A.; Aboagrib, E. A. A.; Zhou, C.; Ma, H. Co-pyrolysis of lignocellulosic and macroalgae biomasses for the production of biochar - A review. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2020**, *297*, 122408.
- (55) Zhang, Y.; Chen, P.; Liu, S.; Peng, P.; Min, M.; Cheng, Y.; et al. Effects of feedstock characteristics on microwave-assisted pyrolysis - A review. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2017**, *230*, 143–151.
- (56) Singh, M.; Salaudeen, S. A.; Gilroyed, B. H.; Al-Salem, S. M.; Dutta, A. A review on co-pyrolysis of biomass with plastics and tires: recent progress, catalyst development, and scaling up potential. *Biomass Convers. Biorefinery* **2023**, *13*, 8747.
- (57) Ananthi, V.; Raja, R.; Carvalho, I. S.; Brindhadevi, K.; Pugazhendhi, A.; Arun, A. A realistic scenario on microalgae based biodiesel production: Third generation biofuel. *Fuel* **2021**, *284*, 118965.
- (58) Kumar, A.; Yan, B.; Tao, J.; Li, J.; Kumari, L.; Oba, B. T.; et al. Influence of waste plastic on pyrolysis of low-lipid microalgae: A study on thermokinetics, behaviors, evolved gas characteristics, and products distribution. *Renew. Energy* **2022**, *185*, 416–430.
- (59) Jazrawi, C.; Biller, P.; He, Y.; Montoya, A.; Ross, A. B.; Maschmeyer, T.; et al. Two-stage hydrothermal liquefaction of a high-protein microalga. *Algal Res.* **2015**, *8*, 15–22.
- (60) Kumar, A.; Yan, B.; Cheng, Z.; Tao, J.; Hassan, M.; Li, J.; et al. Co-pyrolysis of hydrothermally pre-treated microalgae residue and polymeric waste (plastic/tires): Comparative and dynamic analyses of pyrolytic behaviors, kinetics, chars, oils, and in-situ gas emissions. *Fuel* **2023**, *331*, 125814.
- (61) Oliveira, M.; Almeida, M. The why and how of micro(nano)-plastic research. *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.* **2019**, *114*, 196–201.
- (62) Hassan, H.; Lim, J. K.; Hameed, B. H. Recent progress on biomass co-pyrolysis conversion into high-quality bio-oil. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2016**, *221*, 645–655.
- (63) Oyedun, A. O.; Tee, C. Z.; Hanson, S.; Hui, C. W. Thermogravimetric analysis of the pyrolysis characteristics and kinetics of plastics and biomass blends. *Fuel Process. Technol.* **2014**, *128*, 471–481.
- (64) Engamba Ezzo, S. B.; Xiong, Z.; Chaiwat, W.; Kamara, M. F.; Longfei, X.; Xu, J.; et al. Review on synergistic effects during co-pyrolysis of biomass and plastic waste: Significance of operating conditions and interaction mechanism. *Biomass Bioenergy* **2022**, *159*, 106415.
- (65) Vo, T. A.; Tran, Q. K.; Ly, H. V.; Kwon, B.; Hwang, H. T.; Kim, J.; et al. Co-pyrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass and plastics: A comprehensive study on pyrolysis kinetics and characteristics. *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* **2022**, *163*, 105464.
- (66) Martinez, J. D.; Veses, A.; Mastral, A. M.; Murillo, R.; Navarro, M. V.; Puy, N.; et al. Co-pyrolysis of biomass with waste tyres: Upgrading of liquid bio-fuel. *Fuel Process. Technol.* **2014**, *119*, 263–271.
- (67) Ateş, F. Co-pyrolytic Behaviors of Agricultural Wastes. *Energy Sources, Part A Recovery, Util. Environ. Eff.* **2011**, *34*, 111–121.
- (68) Brebu, M.; Ucar, S.; Vasile, C.; Yanik, J. Co-pyrolysis of pine cone with synthetic polymers. *Fuel* **2010**, *89*, 1911–1918.
- (69) Wu, X.; Wu, Y.; Wu, K.; Chen, Y.; Hu, H.; Yang, M. Study on pyrolytic kinetics and behavior: The co-pyrolysis of microalgae and polypropylene. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2015**, *192*, 522–528.
- (70) Pei, X.; Yuan, X.; Zeng, G.; Huang, H.; Wang, J.; Li, H.; et al. Co-liquefaction of microalgae and synthetic polymer mixture in sub and supercritical ethanol. *Fuel Process. Technol.* **2012**, *93*, 35–44.
- (71) Dai, M.; Xu, H.; Yu, Z.; Fang, S.; Chen, L.; Gu, W.; et al. Microwave-assisted fast co-pyrolysis behaviors and products between microalgae and polyvinyl chloride. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* **2018**, *136*, 9–15.
- (72) Grierson, S.; Strezov, V.; Ellem, G.; Mcgregor, R.; Herbertson, J. Thermal characterisation of microalgae under slow pyrolysis conditions. *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* **2009**, *85*, 118–123.

- (73) Yu, J.; Sun, L.; Ma, C.; Qiao, Y.; Yao, H. Thermal degradation of PVC: A review. *Waste Manag.* **2016**, *48*, 300–314.
- (74) Bach, Q.-V.; Chen, W.-H. Pyrolysis characteristics and kinetics of microalgae via thermogravimetric analysis (TGA): A state-of-the-art review. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2017**, *246*, 88–100.
- (75) State, R. N.; Volceanov, A.; Muley, P.; Boldor, D. A review of catalysts used in microwave assisted pyrolysis and gasification. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2019**, *277*, 179–194.
- (76) Chen, C.; Zhao, J.; Fan, D.; Qi, Q.; Zeng, T.; Bi, Y. Microwave-assisted co-pyrolysis of chlorella vulgaris and polypropylene: Characteristic and product distribution analyses. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2022**, *344*, 126279.
- (77) Chen, C.; Fan, D.; Zhao, J.; Qi, Q.; Huang, X.; Zeng, T.; et al. Study on microwave-assisted co-pyrolysis and bio-oil of Chlorella vulgaris with high-density polyethylene under activated carbon. *Energy* **2022**, *247*, 123508.
- (78) Gao, X.; Zhou, Z.; Wang, J.; Tian, H.; Qing, M.; Jiang, L.; et al. Comparative study of the catalytic co-pyrolysis of microalgae (Chlorella Vulgaris) and polypropylene with acid and base catalysts toward valuable chemicals production. *Fuel Process. Technol.* **2023**, *241*, 107520.
- (79) Bahlouli, H. A.; Alghamdi, R.; Manos, G. Coke Characterization and Re-Activation Energy Dynamics of Spent FCC Catalyst in the Catalytic Pyrolysis of Polyolefins. *Catalysts* **2025**, *15*, 862.
- (80) Li, F.; Wang, N.; He, X.; Deng, M.; Yuan, X.; Zhang, H.; et al. Biochar-based catalytic upgrading of plastic waste into liquid fuels towards sustainability. *Commun. Earth Environ.* **2025**, *6*, 329.
- (81) Okaforobah, U. E.; Ezenwa, O. N.; Okeke, J. C.; Okaforobah, C. S. Catalytic Co-Pyrolysis of Biomass and Plastic Waste: A Comprehensive Review. *Int. J. Biomass Util. Sustain. Energy* **2025**, *3*, 82–99.
- (82) Miandad, R.; Nizami, A. S.; Rehan, M.; Barakat, M. A.; Khan, M. I.; Mustafa, A.; et al. Influence of temperature and reaction time on the conversion of polystyrene waste to pyrolysis liquid oil. *Waste Manag.* **2016**, *58*, 250–259.
- (83) Sanahuja-Parejo, O.; Veses, A.; Navarro, M. V.; López, J. M.; Murillo, R.; Callén, M. S.; et al. Drop-in biofuels from the co-pyrolysis of grape seeds and polystyrene. *Chem. Eng. J.* **2019**, *377*, 120246.
- (84) Ma, S.; Lu, J.; Gao, J. Study of the Low Temperature Pyrolysis of PVC. *Energy Fuels* **2002**, *16*, 338–342.
- (85) Suriapparao, D. V.; Hemanth Kumar, T.; Reddy, B. R.; Yerrayya, A.; Srinivas, B. A.; Sivakumar, P.; et al. Role of ZSM5 catalyst and char susceptor on the synthesis of chemicals and hydrocarbons from microwave-assisted in-situ catalytic co-pyrolysis of algae and plastic wastes. *Renew. Energy* **2022**, *181*, 990–999.
- (86) Chen, C.; Fan, D.; Ling, H.; Huang, X.; Yang, G.; Cai, D.; et al. Microwave catalytic co-pyrolysis of Chlorella vulgaris and high density polyethylene over activated carbon supported monometallic: Characteristics and bio-oil analysis. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2022**, *363*, 127881.
- (87) Majid, M.; Chin, B. L. F.; Jawad, Z. A.; Chai, Y. H.; Lam, M. K.; Yusup, S.; et al. Particle swarm optimization and global sensitivity analysis for catalytic co-pyrolysis of Chlorella vulgaris and plastic waste mixtures. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2021**, *329*, 124874.
- (88) Chen, C.; Zhao, J.; Wei, Y.; Huang, X.; Lu, W.; Fan, D.; et al. Influence of graphite/alumina on co-pyrolysis of Chlorella vulgaris and polypropylene for producing bio-oil. *Energy* **2023**, *265*, 126362.
- (89) Stančin, H.; Strezov, V.; Mikulčić, H. Life cycle assessment of alternative fuel production by co-pyrolysis of waste biomass and plastics. *J. Clean Prod.* **2023**, *414*, 137676.
- (90) Wang, C.; Lei, H.; Qian, M.; Huo, E.; Zhao, Y.; Zhang, Q.; et al. Application of highly stable biochar catalysts for efficient pyrolysis of plastics: a readily accessible potential solution to a global waste crisis. *Sustain. Energy Fuels* **2020**, *4*, 4614–4624.
- (91) Wang, Y.; Cao, M.; Lan, W.; Yin, D. Thermal and Oxidative Stability of Biocrude Oil Derived from the Continuous Hydrothermal Liquefaction of Spirulina. *Sustainability* **2024**, *16*, 4884.
- (92) Jiang, L.; Zhou, Z.; Xiang, H.; Yang, Y.; Tian, H.; Wang, J. Characteristics and synergistic effects of co-pyrolysis of microalgae with polypropylene. *Fuel* **2022**, *314*, 122765.
- (93) Dziosa, K.; Makowska, M. Biochar from Chlorella sp. algae as a plant growth activator. *Sci. Rep.* **2025**, *15*, 20700.
- (94) Mariyam, S.; Parthasarathy, P.; Pradhan, S.; Al-Ansari, T.; McKay, G. Co-pyrolysis of biomass and binary single-use plastics: synergy, kinetics, and thermodynamics. *Int. J. Sustain. Energy* **2024**, *43*, 1–22.
- (95) Kong, D.; Wang, S.; Wang, Y.; Chen, H.; Yan, Q.; Gong, Y.; et al. Co-pyrolysis of Chlorella pyrenoidosa and polystyrene: kinetics and product distributions. *J. Energy Inst.* **2025**, *120*, 102109.
- (96) Mirzaei, R.; Shirazvatan, M.; Tavakoli, O. Synergistic effect in Co-pyrolysis of microalgae Chlorella vulgaris and Polyvinyl Chloride: Thermo-kinetic analysis and Thermal behaviour prediction via Machine learning **2025**.
- (97) Wang, Z.; An, S.; Zhao, J.; Sun, P.; Lyu, H.; Kong, W.; et al. Plastic regulates its co-pyrolysis process with biomass: Influencing factors, model calculations, and mechanisms. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* **2022**, *10*, 964936.
- (98) Hou, C.; Zheng, X.; Song, Y.; Shangguan, D.; Zhao, J.; Zhou, X.; et al. Influence of polyethylene chain structure on microwave-assisted co-pyrolysis of polyethylene and microalgae: Nitrogen reduction and oxygen increase effects in bio-oil. *Fuel* **2024**, *374*, 132463.
- (99) Xu, Q.; Mu, L.; Zhang, Y.; Guo, H.; Wu, W.; Sun, Y. Property analysis of co-pyrolysis and aging co-pyrolysis of microalgae and polylactic acid. *Trans. Chin. Soc. Agric. Eng.* **2025**, *21*, 222–230.
- (100) Adachi, W.; Kumagai, S.; Shao, Z.; Saito, Y.; Yoshioka, T. Selective recovery of pyrolyzates of biodegradable (PLA, PHBH) and common plastics (HDPE, PP, PS) during co-pyrolysis under slow heating. *Sci. Rep.* **2024**, *14*, 16476.
- (101) Ghai, H.; Sakhujia, D.; Yadav, S.; Solanki, P.; Putatunda, C.; Bhatia, R. K.; et al. An Overview on Co-Pyrolysis of Biodegradable and Non-Biodegradable Wastes. *Energies* **2022**, *15*, 4168.
- (102) Kristanto, J.; Azis, M. M.; Purwono, S. Multi-distribution activation energy model on slow pyrolysis of cellulose and lignin in TGA/DSC. *Heliyon* **2021**, *7*, No. e07669.
- (103) Belden, E. R.; Rando, M.; Ferrara, O. G.; Himebaugh, E. T.; Skangos, C. A.; Kazantzis, N. K.; et al. Machine Learning Predictions of Oil Yields Obtained by Plastic Pyrolysis and Application to Thermodynamic Analysis. *ACS Eng. Au* **2023**, *3*, 91–101.
- (104) Chen, K.; Xu, Q.; Zhang, S. The Influential Mechanism of Absorbers and Active Metal on Microwave-Assisted Pyrolysis of Sargassum. *Energies* **2025**, *18*, 2723.
- (105) Grierson, S.; Strezov, V.; Bengtsson, J. Life cycle assessment of a microalgae biomass cultivation, bio-oil extraction and pyrolysis processing regime. *Algal Res.* **2013**, *2*, 299–311.
- (106) Gong, X.; Zhang, B.; Zhang, Y.; Huang, Y.; Xu, M. Investigation on Pyrolysis of Low Lipid Microalgae Chlorella vulgaris and Dunaliella salina. *Energy Fuels* **2014**, *28*, 95–103.
- (107) Jena, U.; Das, K. C. Comparative Evaluation of Thermochemical Liquefaction and Pyrolysis for Bio-Oil Production from Microalgae. *Energy Fuels* **2011**, *25*, 5472–5482.
- (108) Chaiwong, K.; Kiatsiroat, T.; Vorayos, N.; Thararax, C. Study of bio-oil and bio-char production from algae by slow pyrolysis. *Biomass Bioenergy* **2013**, *56*, 600–606.
- (109) Du, Z.; Li, Y.; Wang, X.; Wan, Y.; Chen, Q.; Wang, C.; et al. Microwave-assisted pyrolysis of microalgae for biofuel production. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2011**, *102*, 4890–4896.
- (110) Wang, K.; Brown, R. C.; Homsey, S.; Martinez, L.; Sidhu, S. S. Fast pyrolysis of microalgae remnants in a fluidized bed reactor for bio-oil and biochar production. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2013**, *127*, 494–499.
- (111) Miao, X.; Wu, Q.; Yang, C. Fast pyrolysis of microalgae to produce renewable fuels. *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* **2004**, *71*, 855–863.
- (112) Pan, P.; Hu, C.; Yang, W.; Li, Y.; Dong, L.; Zhu, L.; et al. The direct pyrolysis and catalytic pyrolysis of Nannochloropsis sp. residue for renewable bio-oils. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2010**, *101*, 4593–4599.
- (113) Campanella, A.; Harold, M. P. Fast pyrolysis of microalgae in a falling solids reactor: Effects of process variables and zeolite catalysts. *Biomass Bioenergy* **2012**, *46*, 218–232.

(114) Duan, P.; Bai, X.; Xu, Y.; Zhang, A.; Wang, F.; Zhang, L.; et al. Non-catalytic hydrothermal pyrolysis of microalgae to produce liquid biofuels. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2013**, *136*, 626–634.

(115) Saebea, D.; Ruengrit, P.; Arpornwichanop, A.; Patcharavorachot, Y. Gasification of plastic waste for synthesis gas production. *Energy Rep.* **2020**, *6*, 202–207.

(116) Kremer, I.; Tomić, T.; Katančić, Z.; Erceg, M.; Papuga, S.; Vuković, J. P.; et al. Catalytic pyrolysis of mechanically non-recyclable waste plastics mixture: Kinetics and pyrolysis in laboratory-scale reactor. *J. Environ. Manage.* **2021**, *296*, 113145.

(117) Rahman, M. H.; Bhoi, P. R.; Saha, A.; Patil, V.; Adhikari, S. Thermo-catalytic co-pyrolysis of biomass and high-density polyethylene for improving the yield and quality of pyrolysis liquid. *Energy* **2021**, *225*, 120231.